

MIPIE

MAPPING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF POLICY FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION (MIPIE)

An Exploration of Challenges and Opportunities
for Developing Indicators

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**An exploration of challenges and
opportunities for developing indicators**

A project conducted by the
European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education
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FOREWORD

All countries need to track the implementation of new educational policies and legislation. The justifications and pressures for mapping such developments are very clear at:

- International level (as can be seen in the 2006 United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities – UNCRPD – call for data collection and monitoring at State level);
- European level (as outlined in the Lisbon objectives 2010 and also European Council priorities and targets outlined in the ET 2020 strategy);
- National levels (as evidenced through work involving ministerial representatives from 27 European countries. Please see: www.european-agency.org).

The pressures on policy makers to demonstrate how policies are leading towards greater educational inclusion results in the need for the systematic collection of qualitative and quantitative information that answers key questions and can be used longitudinally within countries to map national developments, as well as internationally across countries to compare relative developments.

The work of the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (the Agency) with policy makers in European countries indicates that there are major gaps in the information that is currently available at international, European and national levels:

- The approaches taken by the organisations working in the field and the type of information they provide differ greatly;
- There is no European level agreed approach to information collection that can be used to map implementation of policy for inclusive education;
- Quantitative data alone is not enough to map developments in inclusive education – qualitative information must be collected and made available.

Policy makers working in inclusive education suggest that they need to know what qualitative and quantitative information to collect and the best methods of doing this in order to map the implementation of policies for inclusive education. They need to have agreed signposts to track progress towards educational inclusion, which is a clear priority for all EU member states.

As a result of this perceived priority, in 2009 the ministerial representatives of the Agency member countries agreed to submit a proposal to the European Commission exploring the issues surrounding mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education. In 2010 a grant from the European Commission was awarded to the Agency under Commission Lifelong Learning Programme Comenius funding (agreement number: 510817-2010-LLP-DK-COMENIUS-CAM) for a 1-year project involving 27 Agency member countries: Austria, Belgium (Flemish and French speaking communities), Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom (England, Scotland and Wales).

Over 60 experts – policy makers and data collection experts – as well as representatives of the European Commission, Eurostat and Eurydice have participated in project activities and contributed to this and all other project outputs. Their contributions to the Mapping the Implementation of Policy for Inclusive Education (MIPIE) project work are gratefully acknowledged.

The contact details of all project participants along with all the materials developed during the MIPIE project can be downloaded from the project web area on the Agency website: <http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mipie>

This final project report attempts to document the wide range of discussions, agreements and debates highlighted throughout the MIPIE project activities. It is hoped that the project recommendations presented here provide a detailed agenda for the future short, mid and long term data collection required at national and European levels in relation to mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education.

Cor Meijer

Director

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As a result of the Mapping the Implementation of Policy for Inclusive Education (MIPIE) project work involving over 60 experts from 27 European countries, it is possible to highlight a number of key messages to guide future work in the area. These key messages are the focus of this paper, which presents a summary of the overall findings of the MIPIE project.

There are a number of factors underpinning developments in mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education:

- The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006) as well as the European Disability Strategy 2020 and the ET 2020 strategic objective relating to equity in education all act as key drivers for inclusive education in countries. All of these international policy initiatives require systematic data collection to provide evidence of country compliance with relevant articles and objectives for inclusive education.
- There is a widespread awareness that evidenced-based policy making is critical for the long-term development of systems of inclusive education. Policy makers, data collection experts and researchers are aware of the need for data collection at national level that not only meets the requirements of international policy guidelines, but also works within a shared approach so as to promote a synergy of efforts at national and international levels. However, whilst the need for such data is clear, the methods and procedures for collecting and analysing such data in the best ways is far less clear.
- There is a need for all organisations working at the European level to engage in collaboration and a permanent exchange of information so as to maximise efforts and support national level work in the best possible way.
- There is a need for wide ranging information to be available to policy makers and a variety of complementary approaches to data collection to be taken by different organisations at both national and European levels.

All countries agree that mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education is a complex and multi-faceted task. The concrete proposals outlined in the project work have the potential to be used as the basis for more detailed and long-term research involving the collection of qualitative and quantitative data. This data can be used to support current European level initiatives in this area – notably the Eurostat enquiry focussing upon special needs education – as well as country level work.

A number of specific issues for future data collection at national and European levels can be identified. These along with possible steps to address these issues are presented in the following sections.

The need to develop evidence-based inclusive education policies

Inclusive education can be understood as the presence (access to education and school attendance), participation (quality of the learning experience from the learners' perspective) and achievement (learning processes and outcomes across the curriculum) of all learners in mainstream schools. A clear priority identified by all countries is the need to develop evidence-based policies for inclusive education.

Five key policy requirements relating to data collection emerge from a consideration of the need for evidence on inclusive education at the national level:

- 1 - The need for national level data collection to be anchored within European level agreements;
- 2 - The need to understand the impact of differences in countries' education systems;
- 3 - The need to analyse the effectiveness of inclusive education;
- 4 - The need for data collection to provide evidence relating to quality assurance issues;
- 5 - The need to track the progress of learners in the long-term.

Policy makers need qualitative and quantitative data that informs them about the quality of education of learners with special educational needs (SEN).

These main messages reflect a central recommendation from the World Report on Disability (2011) – the need for countries to develop existing data collection systems for quantitative data, but also conduct detailed and specific qualitative research into cost effectiveness and other quality assurance related issues.

European level work needs to be aligned to the broad concepts of inclusive education as an approach for all learners. This will lead to:

- A re-interpretation of 'traditional' target groups for data collection in order to consider all learners at risk of exclusion, such as migrants, or learners not attending formal education, as well as those with SEN;
- The need to integrate specific data gathering for inclusive education within all 'usual' educational data gathering activities.

European level agreements need to be reached on data collection to track inclusive education possibilities across all lifelong learning phases – from pre-school to adult education opportunities.

Exploring current approaches to data collection at the European level

In examining the current and past work conducted by international organisations, three main approaches to data collection are apparent – data collection based on placement of learners identified as SEN, categories of SEN, or on the allocation of additional resources for SEN.

These approaches are all based on the same highly interconnected core concepts – the identification of SEN and subsequent support to meet a particular need. However, the different emphases in each approach lead to potential strengths and weaknesses.

National level data should be available for EU level comparative work. For this to be done in a meaningful way, there is a need for more clarity on what national data should be collected, how, using what techniques and by who at national and European levels. A 'shared language' for data collection relating to inclusive education based on shared understandings of key concepts at the European level is required.

In the longer term, work at the European level would focus upon data collection that allows policy makers to identify processes that 'work' in inclusive education. The prime focus would be on data that provides evidence of quality in inclusive education. Such work could potentially involve the development of an agreed set of indicators for qualitative data collection.

There is agreement that mapping the implementation of inclusive education at international level faces three main challenges. These relate to issues surrounding definitions, methods and inclusive education policies.

Evidence based policies can only be developed by drawing upon qualitative data that supports quantitative data collection work. However, the demands of current political priorities for quantitative data, particularly at the European level may reduce the emphasis on the collection of high quality qualitative information.

Establishing a shared framework for mapping purposes

The MIPIE project leads to the call for the development of a shared framework for data collection that would build upon existing national data collection procedures, as well as international data collection agreements and procedures. A framework for data collection that would meet the requests of policy makers involved in the MIPIE project would provide information on: the education and learning outcomes of learners with SEN; policy levers shaping these outcomes; the impact of the specific characteristics both of learners and the education systems upon educational outcomes.

Three dimensions underpinning a shared framework can be identified:

- A move to a system based approach for data collection based upon shared concepts and definitions;
- The collection of evidence leading to both quantitative and qualitative benchmarks;
- The use of a multi-level framework for analysing policies at national and international levels.

The proposed shared framework for mapping inclusive education explicitly identifies different foci for quantitative and qualitative data collection relating to:

- Input, process, outputs and outcomes of the education system,
- The system, school, classroom – and through these also – the learner levels.

Such a framework would enable national and international benchmarking to support:

- An understanding of the impact of differences in countries' education systems;
- The identification of similarities in countries' systems for inclusive education;
- The illustration of effects of different elements within systems, such as the degree of centralisation in education, teacher education and training for other education professionals, school autonomy and organisational framework and resources allocated to learners with SEN.

Crucially, such an approach can be built upon by countries to develop data collection in order to monitor learners' rights as well as to monitor the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education.

Monitoring learners' rights

Future data collection must be in line with the UNCRPD (2006), as this is an increasing influence upon legal frameworks for education. Mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education therefore requires indicators providing evidence that education systems are equitable for learners with SEN.

It is possible to identify key rights issues corresponding with the different phases of the input, process, output/outcomes model:

- *Input can be seen to correspond to equity in terms of access* for learners with SEN and their participation in education in non-segregated settings;

- *Process corresponds to equity in relation to educational opportunities* for learners with SEN and the possibilities within the system to provide them with appropriate support to meet their needs;
- *Outputs correspond to equity in terms of achievement opportunities* and possibilities for success in academic and social learning and in the transition opportunities that are open to learners with SEN;
- *Outcomes correspond to equity in relation to personal autonomy* during and after formal education and in particular to the affiliation opportunities open to learners with SEN that support their inclusion into wider society.

Within a comprehensive framework for mapping rights issues, both quantitative and qualitative indicators need to be identified in relation to:

- Participation in education and training;
- Access to support and accommodation;
- Learning success and transition opportunities;
- Affiliation opportunities.

Current and feasible quantitative indicators relating to participation

Existing information at country level indicates that it is possible to identify an indicator on participation rates of school age learners in mainstream education for national and European level data collection work. The indicator that is currently available from existing data focuses upon the *percentage of learners with SEN who are educated in segregated settings*. The operational definition of segregated education agreed upon by European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (the Agency) member countries, is where a learner is formally identified in a country as having SEN and follows education in separate special classes or special schools for the largest part – 80% or more – of their school day.

Work within the MIPIE project suggests that data on learners with SEN in segregated settings is currently the most comparable across countries and that this quantitative data can be used in indicating certain trends in provision and movements towards inclusion.

However, the potential usefulness of any data on participation could be greatly improved by linking it to more systematic data collection at the classroom and/or learner level. It can be seen that indicators more relevant to policy would not only be comparable – both between countries and within longitudinal data collection work – but would focus on participation in inclusive settings, not segregated provision.

In line with the arguments relating to rights and equity for all learners in education, future data collection should take an approach in line with inclusive education as an approach for all learners.

By examining data that might possibly be collected by countries, a feasible indicator could focus upon data relating to the *percentage of all learners of a certain age group (for instance 9 or 14 years old) that follow the mainstream curriculum with their peers of the same age for at least 80% of the time*. Data could be collected by all countries using an agreed approach: either collecting data for all learners of a particular age, or using a random sampling approach.

This indicator has a number of potential advantages: it would provide classroom level data to verify national or regional level data and would focus on all learners (not only those identified as having SEN) therefore emphasising inclusion, not segregation.

As a result of the MIPIE project work, it is argued that quantitative data collection in line with this proposed indicator is feasible and potentially useful and could be pursued at the European level in the near future.

Monitoring the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education

Data that examines the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education would consider a number of areas: initial assessment procedures, to the on-going involvement of learners and their families in educational experiences and the effectiveness of learning environments in overcoming barriers and supporting meaningful learning experiences for all learners.

At national level data should:

- Facilitate planning and the monitoring of resources and personnel,
- Determine the effectiveness of teacher education,
- Evaluate system cost effectiveness.

At school level, data collection should:

- Provide information supporting teachers and school staff to plan and deliver appropriate support and provision;
- Give clear insights into how parents and learners are enabled to take a full part in the educational process.

Examining effectiveness of systems for inclusive education relates input to the key issue of cost effectiveness, with the corresponding descriptor focussing upon resource allocation.

The process of education is related to four key issues and corresponding descriptors:

- 1 - Receptiveness to diversity, as evidenced via to admission data;
- 2 - Quality of learning, as evidenced via data on assessment;
- 3 - Quality of support, as evidenced via data on planning;
- 4 - Teacher effectiveness, as evidenced via data on teaching.

An agenda for European level data collection

Through a consideration all of the proposals from the MIPIE project, a proposed agenda for future developments in data collection at the European level can be identified that is built upon a synergy of efforts at the European and national levels. European level data collection work requires a comprehensive strategy, with activities to be completed in the short, mid and long-term.

In the short term, the data collection strategy should be based upon the current Eurostat enquiry into quantitative data collection for special needs education. It should carefully explore if such data already exists by identifying useful data within existing datasets.

In the mid-term, a European data collection strategy would focus upon the implementation of Article 24 of the UNCRPD and investigate precisely which key information and data may be required, examine whether such data exists and clarify what work is required to gather the data that may additionally be needed.

In the long-term, a data collection strategy should follow a clearly agreed agenda with countries working within a shared framework. MIPIE project experts argued for a comprehensive set of data collection agreements covering concepts, definitions and

methods that could be implemented at the national level as a 'minimum' for countries' data collection work.

This agenda would be based on the premise that inclusive education is a quality imperative and it would work to provide countries with quantitative and qualitative insights into the effectiveness of inclusive education policy and the quality of inclusive education practice in terms of monitoring learners' rights and ensuring equity.

For this European agenda to be enacted, four areas of agreement need to be reached across countries in order to support European level work:

- Identify evidence required at national and at international levels;
- Identify the most effective data available as well as data that still needs to be developed;
- Define coherent data gathering procedures and mechanisms at European and at national level;
- Address comparability issues.

There is a need for synergies at national level between key stakeholders that would be based upon a clear rationale for data collection considering national, regional, school and classroom level data if overall country data is to effectively reflect practice.

Any data collection at the European level must clearly build upon existing national level data collection, directly link to the ET 2020 work and other European strategies and build upon UNESCO, Eurostat and OECD (UOE) data collection systems, as well as those used by the Agency and other international sources.

Future European level work should foster synergies between stakeholders, in the form of closer alignment of data collection activities and work. The synergies needed for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education require work to be framed within a recognised platform, enabling the stakeholders involved in European data collection work to collaborate effectively, to share knowledge and expertise and to define common perspectives. Such a platform – potentially based upon the work of the Agency – would aim to support the work of other European stakeholders in this arena as well as support country data collection work relating to inclusive education.

1. THE MAPPING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF POLICY FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION (MIPIE) PROJECT

The European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (the Agency) is an independent and self-governing organisation, established by the member countries to act as their platform for collaboration in the field of special needs education. The Agency currently has national networks in 27 European countries and is financed by the member countries' Ministries of Education and the European Commission's Lifelong Learning Programme, as one of the 6 institutions pursuing an aim of European interest in the field of education (Jean Monnet Programme).

Presently, the member countries are: Austria, Belgium (Flemish and French speaking communities), Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom (England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales).

The Mapping the Implementation of Policy for Inclusive Education project aims to address a priority need identified by the ministerial representatives of member countries – the development of a set of agreed proposals for future qualitative and quantitative data collection for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education.

Within the project – and this report – the term mapping is understood to refer to the collation of a wide range of indicator and other data sources in order to provide an overall picture of policy situations and developments. On page 85 a Glossary of Key terms is presented in order to clarify the specific terminology used during the project, as well as throughout this report.

1.1 Project outline

The MIPIE project has run from 1st November 2010 to 31st October 2011. The project has been supported by a Project Advisory Group of Agency country representatives from the Flemish and French speaking communities of Belgium and Hungary, Agency staff and an external consultant, Serge Ebersold, National Higher Institute for Training and Research on Special Needs Education (INSHEA), France.

The main project activities have focussed upon two conferences – one in Belgium during December 2010, one in Hungary during 2011. Both conferences were political level events held during the respective countries' hosting of the Presidency of the EU and organised in co-operation with representatives of the Ministries of Education in the two countries.

These two events were used as the main opportunities for information gathering with the target group for the project – that is decision-makers responsible for the implementation of inclusive education policy in the 27 European countries who are members of the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.

In addition, representatives of key European organisations working in the field of policy mapping for mainstream education – Directorate General for Education and Culture (DG-EAC), Eurostat and Eurydice – were invited to join both conferences to present their priorities and work in this field and contribute to the debates with national level policy makers.

The main participants as well as the key target group for the project have been policy makers for inclusive education in European countries. The project has worked with the policy makers nominated by their respective Ministries of Education to act as country project experts within the MIPIE activities.

A further group of participants and a further target group for the project were national level experts on educational data collection. These experts were invited to work with policy makers in formulating proposals relating to the most appropriate methods to be used for meaningful data and information collection for mapping policy implementation for inclusion.

The MIPIE project can essentially be considered an information collection and ‘scoping’ activity. The focus of the project has not been to collect any qualitative or quantitative data; rather to take a first step towards identifying for policy makers what quantitative and in particular qualitative information should be collected and how this can be done in the best way to effectively map the implementation of policy for inclusive education in a meaningful way.

Specific project objectives have been to work with policy makers from 27 European countries in order to:

- Develop a rationale for what information needs to be made available for policy makers;
- Identify what information is already available;
- Highlight the gaps in current information;
- Provide detailed proposals on how the necessary information could be collected in the future for the purposes of national, self-mapping and for European level comparative purposes.

Each of the two conferences organised during the project lifetime had clear goals linked to the development of the eventual project outputs, including this report and the final project recommendations.

The overall goal of the MIPIE project has been to build on existing work being undertaken at national and European levels and, using information collected from countries during the project lifetime, develop recommendations on how this work can be developed in order to outline an agenda for European level data collection to be used for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education.

1.2 Project methodology

A small team of Agency staff working with a project consultant implemented the MIPIE project activities. The work of the project team was guided by a Project Steering Group comprised of nominated country representatives from Belgium – Flemish and French speaking communities – and Hungary.

From a methodological point of view, the MIPIE project focuses upon work conducted before, during and after the two conferences (described in the following sections) involving the nominated experts from all participating countries, in reviewing and exploring the information provided by countries on their data availability and data collection systems. The questionnaire developed to collect this information built upon previous work done by the Agency (notably the 2011 report on Participation in Inclusive Education – a framework for developing indicators) and asked countries to indicate:

- Existing quantitative and qualitative data at national, regional, school, classroom and learner level;
- Breakdowns available;
- Data collection methods and sources;
- Purposes of the data collection.

All the country responses are available from: <http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mapping-the-implementation-of-policy-for-inclusive-education/country-data-collection-work>

All of the MIPIE project activities were conducted within a conceptual framework that draws upon a wide range of work relating to educational mapping at the international level, specifically:

- The European Commission 2010 Lisbon objectives and ET 2020 strategic plans (<http://eurlex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2009:119:0002:0010:EN:PDF>);
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and Eurostat work within their combined UOE (UNESCO – OECD – Eurostat) data collection framework (2004);
- The OECD PISA and the TALIS surveys (OECD, 2000; 2003; 2006; 2010; 2009);
- Research by the Academic Network of Experts on Disability (ANED 2009, 2010);
- Research conducted by European research networks (European Research Associates, 2006; EGREES, 2006);
- The specific work on indicators and statistics for special needs and inclusive education implemented by the OECD within the SENDDD project (OECD, 1999; 2004; 2005; 2007);
- The OECD project Pathways for learners with disabilities to tertiary education and to employment (Ebersold et al, 2010, Ebersold, 2011);
- The indicators for inclusive education project (Agency 2009, 2011) and key principles for inclusive education analyses (Agency 2009, 2011);
- The Special Needs Education Country Data Collection (Agency 2006, 2008, 2010).

1.3 Brussels conference – identifying policy makers’ data collection requirements

The first project conference was held on 2nd and 3rd December 2010, Brussels, Belgium. The aim of this conference was to identify what data and detailed information European policy makers need in order to map developments in the implementation of legislation and policy for inclusion.

During the conference in Belgium, policy makers from the participating countries¹ reflected upon their current information collection and current and future requirements – the ‘what’ of identifying and mapping developments towards inclusive education – and identified key issues, priorities and questions associated with such data collection.

All of the presentations and background materials from the meeting are available from the MIPIE project area on the Agency’s website: www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mipie/brussels-conference

The policy makers debated three key questions:

1. What is the single most important data collection issue the project should focus on?
2. What sort of data do you need to inform you about this issue?

¹ Austria, Belgium (Flemish and French speaking communities), Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom (England).

3. Why is this issue so important within your country context?

During country presentations as well as group and plenary discussions, the participants' inputs were recorded and summarised and then checked and agreed upon. One main message from these discussions was that the starting point for all data collection should be concise policy questions. It was argued that in most countries, data is collected, but it is not guided by policy questions.

Policy makers suggested they need both qualitative and quantitative data that informs them about the quality of the educational experience of learners with special educational needs (SEN), including those with disabilities (as defined by the UNCRPD, 2006). This should include comparable data on the outcomes and effectiveness of different approaches specifically including: data on learners' experiences and achievements and data that demonstrates cost effectiveness of different elements within the education system.

The data needs to map and monitor trends and developments over a period of time and be flexible enough to be interrogated to provide specific answers to specific questions.

In addition, several overall reflections on the requests from policy makers were highlighted during the Brussels conference:

1. The purpose of data collection as providing evidence of effectiveness;
2. The equal value of quantitative and qualitative data;
3. The importance of tracking the progress of young people throughout and beyond their school careers;
4. The need for national level data collection, within European level agreements;
5. The importance of understanding the impact of differences in countries' education systems.

These findings and reflections formed the starting point for preparing the second project conference held in Budapest.

1.4 Budapest conference – identifying responses to policy makers' data collection needs

The second project conference was held on 10th and 11th March 2011, in Budapest, Hungary. The conference was co-hosted by the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education in co-operation with the Hungarian Ministry of National Resources, State Secretariat for Education.

All of the presentations and background materials from the meeting are available: www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mipie/budapest-conference

The conference was officially announced as an event held under the Hungarian Presidency of the European Union (<http://www.eu2011.hu/event/mapping-implementation-policy-inclusive-education-mipie>). The project conference linked to a priority for the Hungarian Government's education strategy – that of reducing unequal access to educational provision and transforming segregated provision into inclusive settings.

In the Budapest conference, the same policy makers were involved, but in addition, each of the participating countries² nominated a national data collection expert to join the event and all discussions. Their expertise informed the project debates regarding the 'how' or methods for future data collection and these experts were considered key participants as well as a further target group for the project.

The Budapest conference built upon the findings from the Brussels conference and aimed to identify *how* the information needed by European policy makers in order to map developments in the implementation of legislation and policy for inclusion can be collected and also to identify the future priorities for this area of work at European and national levels.

Essentially, the Budapest conference was a more technical meeting than the meeting in Brussels. Activities and discussions focused upon the possibilities for collecting the required data, the challenges faced and identifying how these challenges can be overcome.

In preparation for the meeting, country experts drafted overviews of data collection activities in their countries. These overviews provide a rich source of descriptive data regarding work in the participating countries. All overviews were presented in the same tabular format – the table developed within the framework of the Agency project *Participation in inclusive education – a framework for developing indicators* (2011) – which facilitated comparisons during the project analysis phase.

The policy makers and data collection experts highlighted a range of issues that must be considered in relation to potential data collection for mapping purposes. Two main themes were apparent across the group discussions:

- The more inclusive an educational system becomes, the more difficult data collection is, particularly at the learner level;
- The questions policy makers pose cannot be answered with quantitative data alone. Quantitative data should never be presented without explanations of the context for the 'numbers'. However, the nature and focus of qualitative data requires careful explanation.

Many of the general reflections from the project experts participating in the Budapest conference related to the essential purpose of data collection, key questions being identified as:

- Should data collection be focussed upon new information, or confirmation of existing information (with some modifications)?
- What will be compared: learners; expenditure; mainstream versus special school outcomes?

Finally, it was argued that the main aim of collecting data must be seen as improving the education system and not, for example, reducing costs. Any data collected has to create the potential for improvement as well as being meaningful for learners, parents, teachers and policy makers.

² Austria, Belgium (Flemish and French speaking communities), Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom (England, Scotland and Wales).

1.5 The project report

This is the final document developed during the MIPIE project and draws upon a range of information sources collected and analysed throughout the project, including:

- All of the information collected and discussed during the two conferences;
- Overviews of country data collection activities provided by all of the participating countries;
- Information collected via on-line communications between and after the conferences with the project experts;
- A review of relevant research and policy literature relating to mapping and data collection issues (notably the sources outlined in section 1.2).

The main audience for this report is considered to be policy makers for inclusive education, education data collection specialists and EU level decision makers for education. However, it is hoped that the issues raised in this document will also be of interest to policy makers and researchers working in wider education fields not directly related to inclusive or special needs education. It is the intention of the Agency team and the MIPIE Project Steering Group (PSG) that the MIPIE project activities should aim to raise awareness in wider, mainstream education policy debates.

The remainder of this report presents detailed analyses of the following key issues relating to mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education:

- The need to develop evidence based inclusive education policies (chapter 2);
- Exploring current approaches to data collection at the European level (chapter 3);
- Establishing a shared framework for mapping purposes (chapter 4);
- Monitoring learners' rights (chapter 5);
- Monitoring the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education (chapter 6);
- Proposing an agenda for European level data collection (chapter 7).

As well as a full reference list and details of the nominated country experts contributing to this project, this document also contains a Glossary of Key Terms relevant to the issue of mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education.

To accompany this report, a summary of the specific project recommendations has been translated into all 21 Agency member country languages. These and all other project materials and outputs can be accessed from the project web area: <http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mipie>

2. THE NEED TO DEVELOP EVIDENCE BASED INCLUSIVE EDUCATION POLICIES

The Agency report exploring a framework for developing indicators for participation in inclusive education states: *‘Because children don’t count if they are not counted, the capacity building of education systems to improve their data on children at risk of exclusion and marginalisation is an important policy issue internationally.’* (p. 19, 2011).

This argument was used in the initial rationale for the MIPIE project work with two specific assertions being proposed:

- Country systems for educational data collection do not cover all the issues that may arise in relation to inclusive education at international, European as well as national levels;
- Quantitative data alone is not enough to map developments in inclusive education – qualitative information must be collected and made available.

Providing the ‘right’ evidence that can be used to inform policy making for inclusive education policies was a core issue for the country experts who participated in the conference held in Brussels. Discussions showed that the open method of co-ordination – as employed in the ET 2020 strategy – requires benchmarks that can be used to identify policy messages and examples of practice, as well as measure progress in key areas of policy implementation.

This chapter aims to identify the key factors relating to a clear priority identified by country representatives: the need to develop evidence based policies for inclusive education.

Inclusive education can be understood as the presence (access to education and school attendance), participation (quality of the learning experience from the learner perspective) and achievement (learning processes and outcomes across the curriculum) of all learners in mainstream classes (Agency, 2011).

Mapping the implementation of inclusive education policies is a key factor in developing inclusive education systems. Evidence in the form of data permits examination of the effects of policy and practice and provides policy-makers with valuable information that can help them introduce, monitor and evaluate changes and then improve the effectiveness of their policies with the intention of removing barriers to individual learners’ access to education, participation in the learning process and academic and social achievement.

In order to put this policy priority into a clear context, the next section outlines the data collection requirements in relation to people with disabilities generally, as well as specifically in relation to the right to inclusive education as outlined within the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006).

2.1 The need for evidence on inclusive education at an international level

Project participants agreed that the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities UNCRPD (2006) is a stimulus for a process of change and development in the field of inclusive education. Article 1 of the Convention states its purpose as being to: *‘... promote, protect and ensure the full and equal enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by all persons with disabilities, and to promote respect for their inherent dignity.’* (p. 4)

Article 1 defines people with disabilities as including: *‘... those who have long term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairment, which interacts with various barriers in their environment that may hinder their full and effective participation on an equal basis with others.’* (p. 4)

Most EU Member States are signatories to the convention and many have ratified both the Convention and the Optional Protocol. The European Union is also a signatory to both the Convention and the Optional Protocol (for the up to date list see: <http://www.un.org/disabilities/countries.asp?id=166>).

The UNCRPD 2006 is central to the work of policy makers for inclusive education – and therefore central to the considerations of the MIPIE project – in two crucial aspects:

Firstly, Article 24 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006) emphasises that people with disabilities have a right to education without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunity. It goes further outlining: *'States Parties recognise the right of persons with disabilities to education. With a view to realising this right without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunity, States Parties shall ensure an inclusive education system at all levels ... The full development of human potential and sense of dignity and self-worth, and the strengthening of respect for human rights, fundamental freedoms and human diversity ...'* (p. 17).

This article recognises the right of learners with disabilities to education on the basis of equal opportunity, ensuring an inclusive education system at all levels and the facilitation of access to lifelong learning.

Secondly, Article 31 outlines the responsibilities of State Parties with respect to Statistics and Data Collection. States Parties are required to *'... undertake to collect appropriate information, including statistical and research data, to enable them to formulate and implement policies to give effect to the present Convention. The process of collecting and maintaining this information shall:*

(a) Comply with legally established safeguards, including legislation on data protection, to ensure confidentiality and respect for the privacy of persons with disabilities;

(b) Comply with internationally accepted norms to protect human rights and fundamental freedoms and ethical principles in the collection and use of statistics.'

Article 31, continues: *'... The information collected in accordance with this article shall be disaggregated, as appropriate, and used to help assess the implementation of States Parties' obligations under the present Convention and to identify and address the barriers faced by persons with disabilities in exercising their rights ... States Parties shall assume responsibility for the dissemination of these statistics and ensure their accessibility to persons with disabilities and others.'* (p. 23)

Article 33 requires States Parties to establish national/regional monitoring points and independent monitoring mechanisms and *Guidelines for monitoring progress in reaching the CRPD* are specifically outlined within the associated Convention Appendices.

Specific quantitative, but also qualitative data collection in relation to Article 24 is outlined within the *Guidelines for monitoring progress in reaching the CRPD*. It is suggested that with regards to Article 24, State Parties should report on:

- Measures taken to ensure that every child with disabilities has access to early-stage education, and mandatory primary, secondary and higher education;
- Information on the number of boys and girls with disabilities in early-stage education;
- Information on the existing significant differences in the education of boys and girls in the different education levels and whether there are policies and legislation to cater for these differences;

- Legislative and other measures that ensure that schools and materials are accessible and that individualised reasonable accommodation and support required by persons with disabilities is provided to ensure effective education and full inclusion;
- Availability of specific skills-training services for children, adults or teachers who so require in Braille, sign languages, augmentative and alternative communication, mobility and other areas;
- Measures taken for the promotion of the linguistic identity of deaf persons;
- Measures taken to ensure education is delivered in the most appropriate languages, modes, means of communication, and environments for the individual;
- Measures to ensure an adequate training on disability to professionals in the education system, as well as measures to incorporate persons with disabilities in the education team;
- Number and percentage of learners with disabilities in tertiary education;
- Number and percentage of learners with disabilities by gender and fields of study;
- Reasonable accommodation provisions and other measures to ensure access to lifelong learning opportunities;
- Measures taken by the State to ensure early identification of persons with disabilities and their education needs.

However, the intentions for data collection outlined in the UNCPRD do not appear to have been fulfilled. In 2010, the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs published the report *Strategic Action Towards Inclusive Development: Disability, Human Rights and Statistics*. The report reviews disability statistics relevant for monitoring progress towards disability-inclusive development goals, such as the Millennium Development Goals and the UNCPRD 2006. It also examined disability statistics and considered their potential for the monitoring and evaluation of stated UN goals on the lives of people with disabilities and in this aspect, identified a number of areas where there was a perceived need for a stronger partnership: ‘... between data collection and reporting systems regarding disability and development goals.’ (p. 7).

The following recommendations appear to be of particular relevance for the MIPIE project considerations: ‘Member States [should] collect data on disability following international agreements ... National data collected would be widely presented in national reports and would also be reported by Member States to the United Nations using internationally agreed formats that compare persons with and without disabilities; a compilation of these national datasets would then be reviewed, evaluated, published and disseminated by the United Nations through an agreed statistical reporting system on a regular basis; these statistical reports would then be the basis of analytical studies and development monitoring reports undertaken by United Nations agencies and bodies for mainstreaming of disability into human rights, equalization of opportunity and development goals ...’ (p. 8).

2.2 The need for evidence to address key policy concerns at the national level

The main goal of the first project conference in Brussels was to provide policy makers for inclusive education with an opportunity to identify their data collection priorities. All policy makers agreed that they needed clear and relevant evidence on inclusive education that could be used to develop, implement and monitor policies.

They identified five key policy needs relating to data collection that would inform national level policy-making. Each of these themes is presented in the sections below.

2.2.1 The need for national level data collection to be anchored within European level agreements

A recurring theme was the need for European level agreements on data collection. All policy makers agreed that there is a need for clear data on the implementation of policy and practice that allows – where appropriate – the situation of learners with SEN to be compared with that of the general population with breakdowns by age, gender, ethnic minority, socio-economic background, as well as other potentially influential factors.

Sharing information on methods of data collection, as well as making country information transparent and comparable are seen as a good steps forward. However, it is essential that data collection, interpretation and reporting are accessible to a range of different stakeholders.

A recurring issue in debating possible data collection work at the European level is the fact that there is no European definition of the target group. This is a result of differences in each country's own legal definition of SEN and of inclusive education and the resulting differences in target groups for data collection.

European level work needs to be aligned to the broad concept of inclusive education as an approach for all learners. This will lead to:

- A re-interpretation of 'traditional' target groups for data collection in order to consider all learners at risk of exclusion, such as migrants, or learners not attending formal education, as well as those with SEN;
- The need to integrate specific data gathering for inclusive education within all 'usual' educational data gathering activities.

European level agreements need to be reached on data collection to track inclusive education possibilities across all lifelong learning phases – from pre-school to adult education opportunities.

2.2.2 The need to understand the impact of differences in countries' education systems

Comparative data collection and subsequent interpretation of data can be used to identify similarities in countries' systems for inclusive education, but it can also have the important aim of illustrating and explaining differences within systems. During project discussions, a number of potential areas of impact that occur as a result of differences within educational systems were highlighted as being important for further examination:

- Issues related to the size and population of countries;
- The degree of centralisation or decentralisation in countries' education systems;
- Teacher education as well as training for other education professionals;
- The numbers of learners with IEPs; the perceived quality of the implementation of IEPs;
- Class size and staff ratios in inclusive education;
- Provision within non-state sector education;
- Issues relating to trends in the identification of needs and resource allocation for SEN.

Policy makers for inclusive education value data that can be used to develop an understanding of the impact of differences between approaches taken in different countries.

2.2.3 The need to analyse the effectiveness of inclusive education

Experts involved in the project agreed that existing data can empower policy makers to

address the complex issues and questions related to the effectiveness of inclusive education and identify strategies to improve policy and practice. They stressed the equal importance of quantitative and qualitative data being available and highlighted the importance of:

- Regular and systematic data collection systems providing answers to the 'right questions';
- Converging data collection, particularly from research sources in order to identify trends and similar findings from different points of view (i.e. a form of data triangulation);
- Data sources that can be verified, for example via direct sampling of schools;
- More detailed and long-term data on the outcomes of the education system for individual learners.

2.2.4 The need for data collection to provide evidence relating to quality assurance issues

All data collection should provide information that ultimately provides evidence about the effectiveness of the education system. Data should address the question of what works and what does not work and then support policy makers in making 'hard decisions based on that information'.

Evidence based policy making is crucial and all countries are facing the challenge to move from 'experience based policy making' to policy making that is based upon clear and reliable information.

Data to provide evidence of effectiveness needs to support policy makers in considering:

- Quality assurance issues;
- Cost benefit and 'value for money' issues;
- The impact of change within education systems.

Crucially, data needs to provide evidence that the goals countries have for inclusive education are being reached.

2.2.5 The need to track the progress of learners in the long term

Meaningfully tracking the educational 'life histories' of learners with SEN is perceived as being a real challenge. Project experts argued that inclusive education should be about making improvements to all young people's lives, but to demonstrate this it is necessary to map outcomes related to:

- Academic attainments;
- Social relationships and achievements;
- Quality of life issues including self-reliance/autonomy and employment.

Such long-term systematic and detailed data collection would, hopefully, provide insights into the crucial question of how inclusive education supports inclusive societies.

2.3 The need for quantitative and qualitative evidence at national level

Chapter 7 of the World Report on Disability report focuses upon education and children with disabilities. Several sources of information – WHO studies, UNESCO reports, Education for All (EFA) monitoring reports, OECD work, Agency work (SNE country data and thematic studies), as well as specific country research studies – are used. A specific recommendation in the chapter on education is the need to establish monitoring and evaluation systems in relation to development of country policies: '*Data on the numbers of*

learners with disabilities and their educational needs, both in special schools and in mainstream schools, can often be collected through existing service providers. Research is needed on the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of inclusive education'. (p. 226)

This recommendation was agreed upon by policy makers involved in the MIPE project work. However, they went further by arguing that both qualitative and quantitative data is required to address the complex issues and questions related to the effectiveness of inclusive education.

In the majority of countries, existing data does not answer the full range of questions posed by policy makers and improvements in both quantitative data and qualitative data collection are needed. As an outcome of the Brussels conference, the following key messages were agreed upon:

Policy makers need qualitative and quantitative data that informs them about the quality of education of learners with SEN. This will include comparable data on the outcomes and effectiveness of different approaches specifically including:

- Data on learners' experiences and achievements;
- Data that demonstrates cost effectiveness of different elements within the education system.

The data needs to map and monitor trends and developments over a period of time and be flexible enough to be interrogated to provide specific answers to specific questions.

Chapter 2 summary

A clear priority identified by all country representatives within the project is the need to develop evidence-based policies for inclusive education.

Inclusive education can be understood as the presence (access to education and school attendance), participation (quality of the learning experience from the learner perspective) and achievement (learning processes and outcomes across the curriculum) of all learners in mainstream schools.

Project participants agreed that the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities UNCRPD (2006) is a stimulus for a process of change and development in the field of inclusive education and relevant data collection that provides evidence for inclusive education at the international level.

Five key policy needs relating to data collection emerge from a consideration of the need for evidence on inclusive education at the national level:

- 1 - The need for national level data collection to be anchored within European level agreements;
- 2 - The need to understand the impact of differences in countries' education systems;
- 3 - The need to analyse the effectiveness of inclusive education;
- 4 - The need for data collection to provide evidence relating to quality assurance issues;
- 5 - The need to track the progress of learners in the long-term.

Policy makers need qualitative and quantitative data that informs them about the quality of education of learners with SEN.

These main messages reflect a central recommendation from the World Report on Disability (2011) – the need for countries to develop existing data collection systems for quantitative data, but also conduct detailed and specific qualitative research into cost effectiveness and other quality assurance related issues.

3. CURRENT APPROACHES TO DATA COLLECTION AT THE EUROPEAN LEVEL

At the outset of the MIPIE project, two specific assertions in relation to current European data collection work were highlighted:

- There is no European level agreed approach to information collection that can be used to map the implementation of policy for inclusive education;
- The approaches taken by the organisations working in the field and the type of information they provide differ greatly.

The aim of this chapter is to explore these assertions in light of the work with policy makers and data collection experts during the MIPIE project. The main focus is upon European level data collection work and its potential to be used in different ways by countries.

In the Annex to this report, descriptions of the work currently being conducted by seven key international and European organisations involved in educational data collection is presented. Essentially, these provide a descriptive, situation analysis of current data collection activities conducted by: UNESCO; World Health Organisation; OECD; European Commission – the Directorates-General for Education and Culture (DG-EAC) and Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG-EMPL); Eurostat; Eurydice and the Agency. A decision was taken to specifically consider the work of these organisations as they have either been directly involved in, or their work has been repeatedly referred to within the context of the MIPIE project discussions.

In the section below, the descriptive information in the Annex has been used as the basis for a synthesis of information relating to the work of these organisations. This synthesis aims to identify current data collection approaches and their potential contributions to mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education at national and European levels.

3.1 Current approaches to data collection

In examining the current and past data collection work conducted by international organisations, three main approaches are apparent:

- 1 - Data collection based on placement of learners identified as having SEN;
- 2 - Data collection based on categories of SEN;
- 3 - Data collection based on the allocation of additional resources for SEN.

In fact these approaches are all based on the same highly interconnected core concepts – the identification of SEN and subsequent support to meet a particular need. However, the different emphases in each approach lead to potential strengths and weaknesses, which are outlined in the following sections.

3.1.1 Data collection approaches based on placement of learners with SEN

The data collection work of the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education focuses upon two parameters: learners formally recognised in countries as having SEN (identification) and where they are educated (placement). The data collection applies an agreed operational definition of a segregated setting: *‘Segregation refers to education where the learner with special needs follows education in separate special classes or special schools for the largest part (80% or more) of the school day.’* (2010, p. 5)

Across all Agency member countries in total, 3.9% of the compulsory school population is officially identified as having some form of SEN as defined by legislation in the participating countries. However this overall figure hides great differences in countries as is shown in the table below which indicates the percentage of learners in the compulsory school sector recognised as having SEN (in all educational settings). Some countries identify less than 2% of learners as having SEN, while others identify more than 10%:

Table 1: Percentage of learners recognised as having SEN

0–2%	2.1%–4%	4.1%–6%	6.1%–10%	10.1% and above
Sweden	Austria	Belgium (Fr.)	Belgium (Fl.)	Iceland
	France	Cyprus	Czech rep.	Lithuania
	Greece	Denmark	Estonia	
	Luxembourg	Germany	Finland	
	Poland	Hungary	Norway	
	Portugal	Ireland	Slovenia	
	Spain	Latvia	UK (Scotland)	
	UK (England)	Malta		
	UK (Wales)	Netherlands		
		Switzerland		
	(Italy *)	UK (Northern Ireland)		

* Italy = based on 2008 data

In relation to where learners with SEN are educated, across all countries in total, 2.3% of learners within compulsory schooling are educated in either a special school or a separate class in a mainstream school. However, this overall figure again hides differences between countries with some countries placing less than 1% of learners in separate settings, while others place over 4% in separate settings:

Table 2: Percentage of learners educated in separate settings

Up to 1.0%	1.01%–2.0%	2.01%–4.0%	4.01% and above
Cyprus	Austria	Finland	Belgium (Fl.)
Luxembourg	France	Greece	Belgium (Fr.)
Malta	Iceland	Hungary	Czech Republic
Portugal	Ireland	Netherlands	Denmark
Spain	Lithuania		Estonia
	Norway		Germany
	Poland		Latvia
	Slovenia		Switzerland
	Sweden		
	UK (England)		
	UK (Northern Ireland)		
	UK (Scotland)		
(Italy *)	UK (Wales)		

Percentages are calculated using the raw data totals of learners in compulsory education and learners placed in segregated settings

* Italy = based on 2008 data

However, using country definitions of SEN as the basis of data collection presents a number of methodological difficulties that need to be made clear. In addition to issues relating to ‘categories’ of learners within country definitions of SEN (see the next section for a detailed discussion of this issue), country legislation and policy may or may not include a ‘definition’ of what is meant by inclusive education and/or a segregated setting.

The identification of learners placed in fully separate segregated schools is far easier than the identification of those in special, segregated classes in mainstream provision. Despite

the requested application of the agreed operational definition of a segregated setting to data collection, countries may or may not consider learners in special classes in mainstream schools as being educated in inclusive provision.

The age range of compulsory school education is not the same in all countries. Alongside this, some countries 'count' learners outside the compulsory age range if they are enrolled in compulsory sector education, whilst others do not count learners of school age who are either not in school, or who are placed in non-education (e.g. health or social services) provision.

Some countries provide official recognition of a learner's SEN in the form of a decision, certificate, statement or other legal document. However, not all countries collect data relating to learners with an official recognition of SEN. Allied to this point, many countries do not collect data on the numbers of learners in fully inclusive settings that receive some form of SEN support. A number of countries make it clear that official figures relate only to learners receiving extensive support, but that other learners also receive support.

Countries have obvious differences in the numbers and proportions of learners being identified as having SEN; however these differences may not reflect the actual incidence of special educational needs (Agency, 2003) rather these identification rates reflect differences in policies and funding mechanisms. This fact suggests that mapping the implementation of inclusive education requires an agreed shared framework relating to inclusive education.

3.1.2 Data collection approaches based on categories of SEN

As has been made clear in the previous sections, approaches to disability and categorisation systems vary among countries and the profiles of learners identified as having SEN are heterogeneous. The Agency country data collection exercise highlights a number of issues in relation to this situation that require consideration; firstly country legislation and policy may or may not include a 'definition' of what is meant by inclusive education and a segregated setting. Secondly countries include different 'categories' of learners within their definitions of SEN. Different 'categories' of special needs may or may not be covered: disability (sensory, physical, psychological) learning difficulties; behaviour problems; health problems; social disadvantage etc. The Agency work indicates that some countries define only one or two types of special needs. Others categorise learners with special needs in more than ten categories. Most countries distinguish 6–10 types of special needs.

Work from OECD (2007a) OECD and the Centre for Research on Lifelong Learning (CRELL) (2009) and Eurydice (2011) suggests that in addition, learners with temporary learning difficulties, Roma learners, learners with an ethnic minority background, as well as gifted and talented learners may be included in definitions of SEN.

In looking at information available from the Agency, Eurydice, OECD/CRELL and that provided via the MIPIE project, countries' use of categorical systems linked to data collection can be summarised as in the table below.

Table 3: Data collection using 'categories' identified within national definitions of SEN

	Disability categories only	Disability categories plus disadvantaged learners	Disability categories plus gifted and talented learners	Disability categories plus disadvantaged learners and talented learners	Non categorical systems
Austria			X		
Belgium (Flemish)	X	X (1)			

speaking community)					
Belgium (French speaking community)	X				
Cyprus		X (2)			
Czech Republic		X (3)			
Denmark					X
Estonia				X	
Finland	X				
France			X		
Germany	X				
Greece	X (3)				
Hungary	X				
Iceland	X				
Ireland		X (3)			
Latvia		X (3)			
Lithuania	X				
Luxembourg	X				
Malta	X				
Netherlands	X				
Norway					X
Poland		X (3)			
Portugal	X				
Slovenia					
Spain			X		
Sweden		X (3)			
Switzerland		X (5)			
United Kingdom (England)					X (6)
United Kingdom (Scotland)					X
United Kingdom (Wales)					X

Source: OECD/CRELL, 2009; Agency, 2010; Eurybase, 2011

(1) In the SEN-DDD exercise disability categories and disadvantaged learners were included

(2) Greater difficulties compared to the majority of children

(3) Learners at risk and socially disadvantaged learners including ethnic minority groups

(4) This differs from OECD's table developed in 2007. Greece indicated that article 3 of the SEN law (3699/2008) excludes learners with school underachievement due to environmental factors, social disadvantages, linguistic or cultural particularities from the category of learners with disabilities and special educational needs

(5) This includes socially disadvantaged learners including ethnic minority and non-native language speakers

(6) UK (England) categorises by SEN at School Action Plus level and statements by types of need

It is crucial to emphasise that these differences between countries are clearly related to administrative, financial and procedural regulations – they do not reflect variations of the actual incidence and the types of SEN between these countries (Agency, 2003, 2010).

3.1.3 Data collection approaches based on allocation of additional resources

All countries link special educational needs to factors hindering a learner's success at school. Legal definitions of SEN provided by countries (Agency, 2010) show that they all relate special educational need to the need for support that learners may require in their learning as a result of a particular condition that they experience. Depending on the countries, this may include a disability, a learning difficulty, or a social disadvantage (Agency, 2010).

Article 24 of the UNCRPD calls for a focus on the development of systems for inclusive education. This is in line with the 1997 ISCED definition of special needs education which implies that it is necessary to consider all learners receiving additional support for

educational purposes within an inclusive education approach. According to this classification: *'the concept of 'children with special educational needs' extends beyond those who may be included in handicapped categories to cover those who are failing in school for a wide variety of other reasons that are known to be likely to impede a child's optimal progress'* (UNESCO, 1997, p. 42). Including all learners receiving additional support and/or resources would also be in line with the new 2011 ISCED definition – currently being discussed – that defines special needs education as an:

'Education designed to facilitate the learning of individuals who, for a wide variety of reasons, require additional support and adaptive pedagogical methods in order to participate and meet learning objectives in an educational programme. Reasons may include (but are not limited to) disadvantages in physical, behavioural, intellectual, emotional and social capacities. Educational programmes in special needs education may follow a similar curriculum as that offered in the parallel regular education system, however they take individuals' particular needs into account by providing specific resources (e.g. specially trained personnel, equipment, or space) and, if appropriate, modified educational content or learning objectives. These programmes can be offered for individual learners within already existing educational programmes, or be offered as a separate class in the same or separate educational institutions'. (p. 83)

While it can be argued that by describing 'parallel' approaches in education, the proposed definition can be seen to perpetuate the concept of separate systems of provision for different learners, this perspective does highlight the need for data collection in different settings that may exist in countries – i.e. mainstream and separate special settings. This definition may also overcome the potential discrepancies of disability definitions by shifting to an approach focusing on resources delivered by countries at national level and implemented at school level. Such an approach concentrates on the impact of legal frameworks in encouraging policies towards inclusion and refers to the educational restrictions learners have to face, to funding rules and to the capacity to create equitable education systems.

This approach further relates the need for additional resources to address a lack of adaptability within the school's curriculum and to the need for additional human or material resources to stimulate effective and efficient learning for learners. It therefore links the whole concept of special educational needs to a changed system that emphasises the need to monitor policies in order to promote strategies that lead to change (OECD, 2004; OECD, 2005; OECD, 2007; Ebersold and Evans, 2008).

Such an approach has been adopted in the resource based classification system developed by the OECD since the 1990s to provide international comparable data on special needs education (OECD 1998–2007). The categories used in this system for data collection are:

Cross-national category A (the 'disabilities' category) that includes learners who receive additional resources as a result of difficulties in education that have clear organic bases.

Cross-national category B (the 'difficulties' category) encompasses learners who receive additional resources to support their emotional and behaviour difficulties, or specific difficulties in learning. Their educational need arises from problems in interactions between the learner and the educational context.

Cross-national category C (the 'disadvantages' category) involves learners who are in need of additional educational resources to provide additional support to difficulties arising from problems due to aspects of their socio-economic, cultural and/or linguistic background.

This tripartite categorisation system potentially provides data that allows a comparison at international level (Eurostat, 2011). Between 1998³ and 2009⁴, many countries were involved in data collection using the OECD's resource based classification system that was helpful in producing useful data for monitoring and comparison purposes. Data collected provided information on learners receiving additional resources from ISCED level 0 to 3, their type of education (mainstream classes, special classes and special schools), their age and gender. The data collection system also included information on teachers, schools and class size, teacher/learner ratios and whether schools were publicly or privately maintained.

However such a data collection system has weaknesses, some of which are apparent from an examination of the data currently available. Firstly, learners may receive additional resources due to a combination of causes and may therefore be counted twice.

In addition, the approach only takes into account resources delivered by the ministry of education although other ministries may also allocate resources for educational purposes.

Thirdly, the approach does not provide information on the access and opportunities for success available to learners with a disability. Indeed, in some countries, learners with a disability may not have the same opportunities to access education as those with a learning difficulty (Ebersold, 2011). In addition, the type of support and accommodation, as well as their implementation, depends on the type of need that has to be met. Having a breakdown by type of need, therefore, seems crucial.

Fourthly, a breakdown by type of need/disability is in alignment with the definition of disability incorporated in the UNCRPD that covers both children and adults: *'who have long term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairment which interacts with various barriers that may hinder their full and effective participation at equal basis with others'*. (p. 5).

Fifthly, in line with the ISCED definition, such an approach focuses on resource allocation mechanisms and therefore specifically includes those who are entitled to receive human, technical or financial resources for educational purposes. Countries' resource allocation policies result in differences among countries, as those allocating less resources count fewer numbers of learners with SEN than those allocating more resources (OECD, 2004).

Finally, the concept of special needs education is specific to education and may not be applied in the labour market, in the vocational education, or higher education sectors and in some countries, learners with SEN may not be eligible for support when transferring to any of these sectors.

3.2 Applicability of current data to mapping purposes

A key issue considered throughout the MIPIE project has been whether data currently available from international and European organisations can address the data priorities for mapping purposes identified by policy makers. Lee and Mossaad (2010) identify three groups of factors that reduce data comparability at any level of work, in any arena: comparability issues being included or not within the original purpose for which the data was collected; factors related to the analytical methods used such as the definition the

³ The following countries were involved in the OECD's data gathering procedure: Austria, Belgium (Flemish and French speaking communities), Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France (until 2001), Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Luxembourg, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Spain, Slovenia, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

⁴ Covering the Baltic State countries, South Eastern European countries and Malta.

‘target group’; factors related to data collection processes and methods, for example, whether data collection is part of a wider administrative process.

Generally it can be argued that when data currently available from all the organisations described in the preceding sections is considered in terms of relative usefulness for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education, then all three groups of factors identified by Lee and Mossaad are evident:

- Comparability issues in relation to quantitative data have not been successfully addressed in any data collection work of any organisation;
- Data analysis difficulties as a result of the failure to satisfactorily define the ‘target group’ remains an outstanding methodological issue at national, European and international levels;
- Issues emerging as a result of multiple and often widely differing methodologies for data collected at national levels and then used at European or international levels remain.

Within the MIPiE work, it was agreed by policy makers and data collection experts, that the current work of various organisations must be built upon and developed if potential work at the national level is to be effectively applied at the European level.

3.3 National level calls for European level work

As a conclusion to the work completed during the Budapest conference, country policy makers and data collection experts discussed – and via a process of on-line communication – subsequently agreed upon a series of recommendations for data collection for mapping purposes at the European level.

Project experts agreed that any data collection for European level sources must clearly build upon existing national level data collection, as well as directly link to the ET 2020 work and other European strategies. The starting point for European level data will be its applicability to the open method of co-ordination – that is how it can be used for comparative purposes to measure benchmarks.

As such data will be open for scrutiny, there needs to be a clarification of what type of information is useful ‘for public debate’ at the European level – who is the target audience and why do they need this information?

All experts agreed that European level data should only be collected in line with agreed definitions of key terms and parameters. Such definitions could be based on a synopsis of different national definitions to identify differences and commonalities. Alternatively already existing definitions within data collection systems – International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), Eurostat, OECD, International Classification of Function (ICF), Labour Force Survey (LFS) – could be used.

However, the potential consequences of differences between definitions of key terms in different international documents need to be made clear – i.e. UNESCO 2011 definition of special needs education and how this compares with and/or subsumes the UNCRPD 2006 definition of disability.

The project experts’ discussions point towards two potential phases of European data collection work.

As a result of high level, external requests, the focus of immediate work should be upon comparable, quantitative data. This work is essentially the focus of the current Eurostat enquiry into data collection for special needs education.

Project experts were clear that such work requires a careful exploration of whether such data already exists by identifying useful data within existing datasets. Subsequent data collection work would be limited to only collecting data that is required for national level comparative purposes.

Any framework of definitions and methods for data collection applied at the European level must be implemented at the national level as a 'minimum' for countries' data collection work.

Experts suggested that an agreed European approach would need to avoid the risk of focussing only on financial aspects of data collection and would most importantly have to overcome outstanding issues of interpreting internationally agreed definitions at national levels.

In the longer term, work at the European level would focus upon data collection that allows policy makers to identify processes that 'work' in inclusive education. How quality in inclusive education can be evidenced via data would be the prime focus. Such work could potentially involve the development of an agreed set of indicators for qualitative data collection.

Qualitative indicators would be used to explore factors that are known to support inclusive education, for example: teacher education programmes preparing all teachers to work in inclusive settings; the existence of different types of systems of provision and support. They would also demonstrate the outputs of inclusive education, for example: the over or under representation of learners with different needs in certain sectors of education; the numbers/percentages of young people with recognised needs succeeding in public examinations; the destinations/outcomes for learners with SEN.

Long-term data collection work at the European level would work from the premise that inclusive education is a 'quality imperative'. This would necessitate, amongst other factors, the EU wide sampling of provision and approaches as well as the clear definition of desirable outcomes for education other than measurable academic achievements.

3.4 Challenges for future European level data collection work

In relation to the priorities for European data collection identified by policy makers working in the MIPIE project, there is a general agreement that mapping the implementation of inclusive education at international level faces several challenges. It was suggested at the meetings held within this project that identifying gaps in current data collection work was a useful first step to highlighting challenges and identifying factors allowing them to be overcome.

Some key challenges are outlined in the previous sections. However, in summary three main areas of challenge are apparent, relating to issues surrounding definitions, methods and inclusive education policies. Each of these is considered in the sections below.

3.4.1 Challenges relating to definition issues

All participants within the MIPIE project – including representatives of international organisations – agreed that definitions of disability and special educational needs require careful consideration. A recurring issue in debating current and potential work at European level is the fact that there is no clear definition of the target group for data collection.

At present:

- There are no international or European level agreements that are being used for national level data collection;

- Data collection work being conducted within the UOE system, as well as by OECD, Eurydice and Agency all use national level data whose starting point is national level definitions of SEN;
- National data is applied to the various internationally generated concepts or indicators being used by the different organisations, rather than internationally generated concepts being used for data collection at national level.

The imposition of 'external' definitions of disability or SEN to country based data collection is recognised by countries participating in the MIPIE project as having significant methodological difficulties in practice. The education systems (policies and practice) that direct special needs and inclusive education provision in countries have evolved over time, within very specific contexts and are therefore highly individual. It is for this reason that the Agency member and observer countries have agreed that the most useful approach to collecting any form of data on special needs education is to take a 'bottom-up' approach that uses the country's own legal definition of SEN as the basis for data collection.

3.4.2 Challenges relating to data collection issues

As well as definition issues, methodological difficulties may specifically lie in data collection procedures. Drawing on information provided by experts participating in the project, systems or activities relating to data collection are very diverse among countries. Very few countries collect data that allow an analysis of admission, process and outcomes issues.

Information provided by countries to the project country data collection survey shows that data sources vary among countries. While some countries gather data on learners with SEN within their education information system, others collect them from their special education department/administration information system and are unable to identify precisely those enrolled in mainstream settings. A third group gather data from several information providers and may face comparability issues due to the definitions of disability/SEN being used by the various sources, as well as in relation to the data collection procedure.

The meetings held in Brussels and in Budapest revealed that a number of countries face systemic problems with data collection that result in an inability to standardise country level information collected from decentralised settings of different kinds. It also appeared that for a number of countries, laws prohibiting data collection in certain areas due to privacy and/or data protection legislation presented obstacles to data collection that can only be 'worked around' and not directly addressed.

It can be argued that in many countries, for example Norway, the more inclusive a system becomes, the more data collection relating to learners with SEN becomes problematic. Another example is given by Iceland who explains that gathering data on transition from compulsory to upper secondary school is only possible for those learners enrolled in special schools or in special classes.

Some countries identified difficulties with data on an individual level concerning learners with SEN, due to the legislation (e.g. personal data acts) that prohibit the processing of data concerning health issues. There are very different policy approaches to this issue in different countries.

The identification of learners who are of school age, but who are either not in any form of education provision, or who are placed in non-educational provision (i.e. health or social sector institutions) is a further challenge. Data on learners who are 'not in school' for different reasons may be unavailable for educational analysis purposes.

Experts highlighted the constraints that may underpin new data collection procedures. These constraints are not only financial – collecting and analysing qualitative data is often considered more expensive and time-consuming than collecting quantitative data – but also related to the potential danger of overloading teachers with additional tasks and the difficulties that may exist in fostering positive attitudes towards data collection within school management teams. Experts argued that there is a clear need to link any proposed new data collection to their existing systems of national data collection.

3.4.3 Challenges relating to inclusive education policy issues

It can be seen that the methodological difficulties outlined above are related to the topic of inclusive education. Experts involved in the project highlighted the need to clarify whether inclusion in education is ‘an absolute state’ or if ‘levels of inclusion’ can be identified and data needs to be collected accordingly.

Building on the work of Ainscow et al (2006), a number of key policy tensions in the field were identified during the Budapest conference including:

- Integrated versus separated strands of inclusion;
- An inclusive versus standards agenda approach to education;
- Teaching and supporting diversity versus special needs education;
- Long-term sustainable change versus short term targets;
- Attending to conditions for teaching and learning versus attending to outcomes;
- Rational versus reactive planning; commitment to inclusive values versus compliance to directives.

In addition, there is no one accepted ‘best approach’ to inclusive education and participants in the meetings felt that any indicators should not limit countries to specific ways of achieving inclusive education. While comparisons of experiences across countries can be beneficial, such practice may require an agreed set of indicators applicable to all countries’ contexts, rather than the same set of indicators for all countries.

Due to the complexity of the specific contexts of countries’ systems for inclusive and special needs education, it is extremely hard for any potential data collection at international level to account for the impact of differences in countries’ education systems. However, despite these difficulties, attempts should still be made to place data in clear and understandable wider contexts. Although organisations currently working in this field agree with such action, there is a potential risk that the calls at EU level for statistical indicator information relating to developments in inclusive education may result in simplistic interpretations of country situations.

Chapter 3 summary

In examining the current and past work conducted by international organisations, three main approaches to data collection are apparent:

- 1 - Data collection based on placement of learners identified as SEN;
- 2 - Data collection based on categories of SEN;
- 3 - Data collection based on the allocation of additional resources for SEN.

These approaches are all based on the same highly interconnected core concepts – the identification of SEN and subsequent support to meet a particular need. However, the different emphases in each approach lead to potential strengths and weaknesses.

It was agreed by policy makers and data collection experts that the current work of various organisations must be built upon and developed if potential work at the national level is to be effectively applied at the European level.

The country experts suggest that national level data should be available for EU level comparative work. For this to be done in a meaningful way, there is a need for more clarity on what national data should be collected and how this should be done at national and European levels. A 'shared language' for data collection relating to inclusive education based on shared understandings of key concepts at the European level is required.

In the longer term, work at the European level would focus upon data collection that allows policy makers to identify processes that 'work' in inclusive education. The prime focus would be on data that provides evidence of quality in inclusive education. Such work could potentially involve the development of an agreed set of indicators for qualitative data collection.

There is agreement that mapping the implementation of inclusive education at international level faces several challenges. Three main areas of challenges are apparent relating to issues surrounding definitions, methods and inclusive education policies.

The MIPIE project experts suggest that evidence based policies can only be developed by drawing upon qualitative data that supports quantitative data collection work. However it can be argued that current political priorities particularly at the EU level requiring quantitative data may reduce the emphasis being placed upon the collection of high quality qualitative information.

4. ESTABLISHING A SHARED FRAMEWORK FOR MAPPING PURPOSES

Mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education requires a framework that is accepted by stakeholders at national and European levels. This is stressed within the Agency study *Participation in inclusive education – a framework for developing indicators* (2011), but was also highlighted within the European arena of the Brussels conference held in December 2010, as well as of the Budapest conference held in March 2011.

During both of these events, a recurring theme was the need for national level data to be collected and used within European level agreements for data collection. All policy makers agreed upon the need for the identification of common features within inclusive education across countries and emphasised the need for clear data on policy implementation and practice that can be used as an inspiration for others.

However, as indicated in the previous chapter, there is currently no overall framework within which national data can be used for comparative work at the EU level and there is a need for more clarity about which data should be collected and by whom, as well as on the methods to be used at national and European levels.

Within their debates, MIPIE project experts argued for the development of a shared framework for data collection that would build upon:

- Existing national data collection procedures;
- International conventions such as the UNCRPD 2006 and agreements such as the ISCED definition (UNESCO, 1997);
- The currently used data collection procedures of the UNESCO, OECD and Eurostat (UOE, 2004) as well as those used by the Agency (2010).

Three dimensions would underpin such a shared framework:

- A move to a system based approach for data collection based upon shared concepts and definitions;
- The collection of evidence leading to both quantitative and qualitative benchmarks;
- The use of a multi-level framework for analysing policies at national and international levels.

Each of these dimensions is discussed in the following sections.

4.1 A system-based approach for data collection based upon shared concepts and definitions

Most countries across Europe support the development of inclusive education. The Agency's work, as well as international research conducted on this issue, shows that there is a strong trend towards including learners in need of additional educational support in mainstream schools and providing educational settings and learners with a varying degree of support (OECD, 1999; Ebersold, 2010; Agency, 2003, 2009, 2011).

This trend is strongly supported by international organisations. Article 24 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities states that the education people with disabilities are entitled to is in principle inclusive in nature. According to this article, 'all children with disabilities' must have access to a quality and inclusive education in the community in which they live and have the right to attend the school they would go to if they did not have a disability.

UNESCO IBE (2009) calls upon member states to: *'adopt an inclusive education approach in the design, implementation, monitoring and assessment of educational policies as a way to further accelerate the attainment of Education for All (EFA) goals as well as to contribute to building more inclusive societies.'* (p. 3). It understands inclusive education as a philosophy that assumes that learners with special educational needs – including those with disabilities – have the same right to education as the others with access to ordinary schools. This requires that the education system provides all learners, including those identified as having special educational needs, with the possibility to learn together without discrimination (UNESCO, 1994). In doing so, education systems must take into account the diversity of learner needs.

The UNESCO Policy Guidelines on Inclusion in Education (2009) stress that inclusion and quality are reciprocal – that an inclusive ethos can make a significant contribution to the quality of education for all learners. The role of inclusive education in the development of a more just, equal and democratic society where diversity is celebrated is also considered to be of increasing importance. Such development involves principles such as equal opportunities, non-discrimination and universal access and needs to take account, in particular, of the individual needs of learners who are at risk of social exclusion and marginalisation.

Within the Council of the European Union (2009) it is emphasised that: *'Education should promote intercultural competences, democratic values and respect for fundamental rights and the environment, as well as combat all forms of discrimination, equipping all young people to interact positively with their peers from diverse backgrounds'* (p. 3).

This is reinforced by the Conclusions of the Council of Ministers (2010) on the social dimension of education and training which notes that education systems across the EU need to ensure both equity and excellence and recognise that improving educational attainment and key competences for all are crucial not only to economic growth and competitiveness but also to reducing poverty and fostering social inclusion.

Fostering inclusive participation of people with disabilities and working towards their full enjoyment of equal fundamental rights is a core objective of European Union policy. European level strategy and co-operation recognises that 'education and training are essential to the development and success of today's knowledge society and economy' and this is underlined in Education and Training 2020 strategy (http://ec.europa.eu/education/lifelong-learning-policy/doc28_en.htm).

There is evidence of policy linkage between employment, disability and education in some countries (including evidence from previous ANED country reports (2010, 2011) on employment and social inclusion). Shared objectives and a framework for co-operation between countries were agreed by Education Ministers under the title Education and Training 2010 (including benchmarks, reporting processes and exchanges of good practice).

The ET 2020 work programme includes a commitment to ensuring that the European Union's education and training systems become 'accessible to all'. In particular, Objective 2.3 (Supporting active citizenship, equal opportunities and social cohesion), notes that equal access to education and training for all needs to be reinforced and that Member states should pay special attention to supporting vulnerable groups and individuals, particularly those with disabilities or learning difficulties.

The UNCRPD requires data collection related to Article 24 that links the implementation of the right to education with the ability of education systems to adapt educational environments to learner's needs. Such a framework calls for a system based approach,

allowing the identification of the barriers that hinder access to education. This goes together with the allocation of the resources that are necessary for overcoming those barriers, irrespective of the type or 'category' of a learner's need.

In a provision-based approach, data collection would therefore focus on the learning environment and support policy makers in moving from experience-based policy making to evidence-based policy making. Such an approach would provide insight into learners' experiences of inclusive education to ensure that learners with SEN complete their education and participate actively in society.

4.2 Evidence leading to both quantitative and qualitative benchmarks

In the Brussels and Budapest conferences, both policy makers and data collection specialists involved in the project stressed the need for quantitative and qualitative data collection within a framework that provides information on the education and learning outcomes of learners with SEN; policy levers shaping these outcomes and the impact of the specific characteristics both of learners and the education systems upon educational outcomes.

The project experts suggested that data collection should inform the implementation of inclusive education by supporting an understanding of learning outcomes linked to inputs and processes at the level of individuals and institutions.

They agreed with the proposal to frame their country data collection work within the *input, process* and *outcome* model generally used by international agencies (such as the European Commission and the OECD) to analyse the effectiveness and equity of education systems. Such an approach is also advocated by the Agency in the indicators for inclusive education project work (2009, 2011).

As part of project activities, they provided detailed information on their current national data collection work, using a template based on an input, process, outcome model. As a result of using such an approach to consider their current work, a number of clear messages regarding potential future data collection were highlighted by project experts.

4.2.1 Data on system input, process and outcomes

In relation to *input*, during the MIPIE project country experts suggested that data collection should include information on learners identified as receiving support for their SEN. This includes information on their profiles (age, gender, type of need), their participation opportunities in education (enrolment) and on their transition experiences between education levels, etc.

As to *process*, countries suggested that data collection should also provide information on the added value of inclusive education compared to other forms of provision. Some country experts argued that data should provide evidence based arguments for inclusive education or special education, describing the quality of provision in different settings (inclusive classes or separate classes or schools) as well as learners' experiences in both inclusive education and special education. Such data would potentially also inform debates regarding the value of inclusive education for all learners, not just those identified as having SEN.

In relation to data considering system *outcomes*, two possible aspects were identified. Country experts suggested that data collection should deliver clear and reliable information on *outputs* in terms of the effectiveness of the education system for learners with SEN. Data should therefore examine if inclusive education for learners with SEN guarantees equal opportunities in terms of access, academic and social learning attainments and achievements. It should also allow performance to be monitored by

looking at quality assurance issues as well as cost-benefit and ‘value for money’ issues. This implies the need for information on the effectiveness of support in meeting learners’ real needs and fostering their inclusion in the school environment.

A further aspect within a consideration of *outcomes* is that of opportunities open to learners within SEN after they leave school. Experts suggested that data collection should explore transition to employment, further educational opportunities and wider inclusion opportunities as well as the education system’s ability to enable learners to meet long-term labour market challenges and requirements.

Country experts agreed that data should support the monitoring of policies so that trends can be easily and regularly identified. The country experts agreed that meaningfully tracking the educational ‘life stories’ of learners with SEN – despite the challenges such an issue may encompass – is necessary. Although it should be acknowledged that gathering data via life-stories would involve longitudinal work, over a very long period of time, such systematic and detailed data collection would, potentially, provide insights into the crucial question of how inclusive education supports inclusive societies.

4.2.2 Qualitative data exploring barriers to inclusive education

In order to address the issues clearly identified by the MIPIE project country experts, data collection cannot focus only on quantitative data. An understanding of inclusive education cannot be reduced to a consideration of standards in easily quantifiable aspects of a learner’s educational achievements, such as measurements of reading, writing and simple arithmetic abilities.

Research reveals that the development of inclusive education systems depends on: policy makers’ commitment to inclusive education, schools’ ability to include diversity issues in their policies, supportive environments for teachers, learners and parents, and most importantly on the removal of barriers to learners’ participation to the learning process (OECD, 1999; Ebersold, 2011, Agency, 2009, 2011). Research from the OECD (1999) highlights barriers to the development of inclusive education on three levels.

Barriers at a policy level, are related to: the absence of a comprehensive policy to advance inclusive education and in particular to limited early childhood intervention; the absence of overall legislation including non-discrimination legislation; a lack of awareness of the rights of people with disabilities; inadequate funding mechanisms; inappropriate teacher training systems and inaccessible physical environments, both within and outside of the school setting.

Barriers at the school level result from: the absence of disability issues in policies and action plans; limited partnership between schools, parents, relevant support services and/or the local community; inadequate school based individualised learner assessment; limited access to information and communication technologies; the absence of outcome based curriculum development; the lack of flexibility within curricula, organisation and support and the lack of flexible examination arrangements.

At the classroom level, barriers to developing inclusive education are due to: ineffective multi-disciplinary teamwork enabling a holistic educational approach; a high learner to adult ratio, including the absence of part time or a full time classroom assistant support; inflexible class size and composition; a lack of curriculum differentiation and inappropriate teaching materials; inappropriate support and a lack of parental and wider community involvement.

These and potentially other factors require detailed and long-term data collection and analysis from within countries’ own perspectives and contexts.

4.2.3 Data that exemplifies differences in country situations

The factors outlined in the previous section depend on countries' overall education systems, as well as on the specific contexts of their systems for inclusive and special needs education. These factors highlight the need for collected data to be situated within a clear understanding of the wider educational context, in order to avoid simplistic interpretations of country situations that may result from purely statistical indicators relating to changes in special and inclusive education.

Countries experts clearly state that there is a need for qualitative information in addition to quantitative data to address the complex issues and questions related to inclusive education and to identify key factors supporting inclusive practice at different levels of their education systems – national level, school environment level and at the level of the classroom.

The MIPiE project experts argue that their request for European level agreements upon data collection is in fact highly inter-connected to their request for recognising specific country contexts, as European level agreements cannot be developed without first establishing a clear understanding of the differences existing in countries' education systems.

The experts' assertions go further, as they argue that a clarification of country commitments to the implementation of inclusive education is required and that this can be achieved through monitoring policies and practice using a shared framework of quantitative and qualitative benchmarks linked to core issues for inclusive education.

These benchmarks should build upon priority areas identified in both the 2010 Lisbon objectives and EU 2020 strategies and would explore the key issues in relation to early childhood education, completion of upper secondary education, achievement in reading literacy in order to compare the situation of learners with SEN with the general population.

In line with various research implemented by the OECD on factors impacting on the quality of inclusive education as well as the work done by the Agency on the development of a set of indicators, benchmarks could include qualitative issues, focussing upon one or more of the following areas agreed by countries within the Agency indicators project (Agency, 2009, p. 24):

- Legislation and balance/consistency between inclusive education and other policy initiatives;
- Clear national policy on inclusive education;
- Value statements underlying the curriculum as a point of reference (curriculum, certification);
- Inclusive education assessment systems;
- Participation of learners in decision making;
- Connection between inclusive education and lifelong learning/early childhood intervention;
- Incentives in resources and support allocation; pre-resourcing of schools versus resourcing based upon diagnosis of needs;
- Financing and processes linked to funding mechanisms;
- Inter-sectoral cross-sectoral co-operation;
- Inter-disciplinary support systems;

- Teacher education and training of professionals;
- Systems/cultures that encourage collaboration and teamwork among teachers;
- Differentiation, diversity and multicultural education in the classroom;
- Systems of accountability.

4.3 A multilevel framework for analysing policies at national and international levels

Within their discussions in the Brussels Conference, the MIPIE project experts suggested that three potential levels of national data collection should be considered as being of importance to policy makers.

1 - *System level data*: that helps to improve the education process is required. Such data would aim to provide evidence that addresses key policy issues.

2 - *School level data*: that would give *insights into the quality of school life for all stakeholders*.

3 - *Learner outcomes level data*: The goal of collecting such data would be to explore the effectiveness of resource allocation in the short, medium and long term for learners.

This approach links to that developed by the Agency in its previous work on indicators (2009, 2011) and is potentially a useful framework in attempting to define benchmarks and the related indicators required at both national and international levels for monitoring developments. This approach looks at the process of education over time – from the admission of the learner into school, to his/her transition to work and social inclusion – and proposes the need for monitoring mechanisms relating to the input, the process and the outcome of education to understand policy and practice.

Within the Agency work, inputs are defined as: *'all aspects provided to the system to achieve a certain outcome and include financial resources, legislation related to education as well as the qualification level of teachers or any infra-structural issues'* (Agency, 2009, p. 14). In line with this model, input also potentially includes admission policies and strategies that underpin the continuity and the coherence of educational pathways at transition phases, as well as learners' success opportunities and inclusion into a school community (Ebersold, 2011).

Process refers to: *'all educational activities, including procedures, state/school/district practice or classroom instructional practice'* transforming inputs into outputs and outcomes (Agency, 2009, p. 15). This aspect of the model corresponds to MIPIE country experts' request to have evidence that learners' needs are being met by examining data relating to a number of crucial factors in education such as:

- Assessment activities (identification of needs, understanding difference, testing and assessing for planning purposes, monitoring learning);
- Planning activities (decision-making processes regarding the curriculum and resource allocation, individual educational planning);
- Teaching activities (pedagogy, instruction, teaching arrangements, intervention).

Within the model: *'outputs describe efficiency measures such as curricular achievements, academic attainment while outcomes emphasize the affiliation effect of inclusive education in terms of independence and citizenship'* (p. 15). Education processes transform these inputs and resources into outputs and outcomes.

The model put forward in the work is a multilevel approach proposing that the quality of inclusive education must be examined according to four interacting levels: macro, meso,

micro and person. Such a multi-level approach relates the quality of inclusive education to the relationship between policy, practice and individuals. It therefore takes into account the different issues relating to the involvement of learners, parents and their families at all levels of the educational process (Agency, 2011).

Country information collected during the MIPIE project covered these four levels. Using the 'matrix' to organise information on participation proposed in the 2011 report (p. 22) a table relating to current information collection activities in participating countries was completed. An analysis of the information provided by countries indicates the following:

- The *macro* level refers to the system of education, that is policy and practice at *national or regional level*. Information provided by the MIPIE project experts indicates that data relating to macro level issues must aim to provide evidence that addresses key policy concerns: for example how inclusive policy supports inclusive practice; the effectiveness of different placements (special – mainstream schools) and educational approaches; the potential added value of inclusive education; how the system empowers learners and their parents.

- The *meso* level encompasses policies and practice at *school level* and data collected in line with this level must focus upon the possibility of creating inclusive cultures within the school as well as promoting learners' inclusion. Data relating to this level should give insights into the quality of school life for all stakeholders. Potential issues to be considered would include: school wide approaches to valuing diversity, disability and support issues; how schools effectively involve parents; how the school takes the wider home and community environment into account in planning learning and teaching; how social inclusion is supported in educational processes; how management styles supports inclusive cultures and practice.

- The *micro* level that relates to educational practice and interactions at *classroom level* focuses on the organisation of learning and the mobilisation of resources. Data exemplifying this level would provide information on: professionals, how they are organised and what they do; teachers' attitudes towards all learners and their skills for meeting diverse needs.

- The *person* level covers both *teachers*, but most importantly *learners* with data giving insights into: individuals' involvement and engagement with education; academic success for learners; personal and social well-being, as well as feelings of satisfaction. Data would aim to examine how learners with SEN are active participants in the life of the school community, and crucially how participatory relationships act as mediators between policy, practice and individuals.

Inclusive education policies – in contrast with integration policies – focus upon ensuring equity of opportunity and effectiveness of schools in terms of access, participation in meaningful learning, achievement and social involvement. Mapping inclusive education policies therefore requires monitoring in relation to both learners' rights and system effectiveness in order to clearly identify if education systems provide learners with SEN to the fullest extent possible with the same opportunities as their peers, enabling them to acquire qualifications and skills required by the labour market and empower them to be included into society.

By looking across all of the key issues and proposals presented in this chapter in line with the specific information identified in the analysis of country data, it is suggested that a shared framework for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education would need to consider each of the elements presented in the composite table below.

Table 4: Elements within mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education

Policy/practice	Input	Process of education			Output	Outcomes
	Admission	Assessment	Planning	Teaching and support	Attainments and achievements	Opportunities, transition and affiliation
National/regional level (macro)						
School level (meso)						
Classroom level (micro)						
Learner level (person)						

This framework has the potential to be further developed to identify areas for data collection in relation to:

- Ensuring that all learners' rights are met;
- Examining the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education.

These factors were identified by the MIPIE project experts as being of critical importance for systematic data collection and analysis. These issues are the focus of the following chapters.

Chapter 4 summary

The MIPIE project leads to a call for the development of a shared framework for data collection that would build upon existing national data collection procedures, as well as international data collection agreements and procedures.

Three dimensions underpinning such a shared framework can be identified:

- A move to a system based approach for data collection based upon shared concepts and definitions;
- The collection of evidence leading to both quantitative and qualitative benchmarks;
- The use of a multi-level framework for analysing policies at national and international levels.

The proposed shared framework for mapping inclusive education explicitly identifies different foci for quantitative and qualitative data collection relating to:

- Input, process, outputs and outcomes of the education system;
- The system, school, classroom and through these also the learner levels.

Such a framework enables national and international benchmarking to support:

- An understanding of the impact of differences in countries' education systems;
- The identification of similarities in countries' systems for inclusive education;
- The illustration of effects of different elements within systems, such as the degree of centralisation in education, teacher education and training for other education professionals, school autonomy and organisational framework, resources allocated to learners with SEN.

Crucially, such an approach can be built upon to allow countries to develop data collection in order to monitor learners' rights as well as the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education.

5. MONITORING LEARNERS' RIGHTS

In the previous chapter, a framework for data gathering for mapping purposes was proposed. In this chapter, the first of two essential content areas that need to be incorporated within a mapping framework is discussed – that of monitoring learners' rights.

Article 1 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2007) states that: *'Human dignity is inviolable. It must be respected and protected.'* Article 26 states that: *'the EU recognises and respects the right of persons with disabilities to benefit from measures designed to ensure their independence, social and occupational integration and participation in the life of the community.'* (p. 8).

The policy maker experts participating in the MIPIE Brussels conference indicated that future data collection must be in line with the UNCRPD 2006, as this increasingly has an influence upon their legal frameworks for education. Data collection must provide evidence about the implementation of the rights of persons with disabilities and the educational opportunities they are entitled to.

Monitoring learners' rights to equal opportunities within education is essentially an equity issue and mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education therefore requires indicators providing evidence of the ability of education systems to be equitable and non-discriminatory for learners with SEN.

The Council of Europe (2009) suggests that equity implies: *'activities to the benefit of all, targeting each individual'* (p. 46) and states that by using the term equity, *'inclusion may be understood not just as adding on to existing structures, but as a process of transforming societies, communities and institutions such as schools to become diversity-sensitive.'* (op. cit.).

Garcia-Huidobro (2005) suggests that equity must be at the centre of general policy decisions and not limited to peripheral policies oriented to correct the effects of general policies that are not in line with an inclusive approach. UNESCO IBE (2008) highlights the importance of inclusion in education as a means of promoting equity and addressing increasing inequality and cultural fragmentation.

Building upon the framework outlined in the previous chapter, it is possible to identify *key rights issues* corresponding to the different phases of the input, process, output/outcomes model. Then, in relation to each of these key rights issues, a *descriptor* can be identified. These descriptors correspond to areas of data collection work that are already in evidence in countries to a greater or lesser extent.

Within a comprehensive framework for mapping rights issues, for each descriptor, both *quantitative and qualitative indicators* need to be identified.

Such a model is presented in the table below.

Table 5: Issues and descriptors relating to monitoring learners' rights

	Input		Process of education		Output		Outcomes	
Key issues corresponding to rights	Equity in terms of access		Equity in relation to educational opportunities		Equity in terms of achievement opportunities		Equity in relation to personal autonomy	
Descriptors corresponding to rights	Participation in education		Access to appropriate support		Learning success and transition opportunities		Affiliation opportunities	
Indicators	Qn	Ql	Qn	Ql	Qn	Ql	Qn	Ql

National/regional level								
School level								
Classroom level								
Learner level								

Qn – Quantitative Ql – Qualitative

In terms of monitoring learners’ rights the model relates:

Input to equity of access for learners with SEN in terms of their *participation in education* in non-segregated settings;

Process to equity in relation to educational opportunities for learners with SEN and the possibilities within the system to provide them with *appropriate support* to meet their needs;

Outputs to equity in terms of achievement opportunities and possibilities for *learning success and transition opportunities* open to learners with SEN;

Outcomes to equity in relation to personal autonomy during and after formal education and in particular the *affiliation opportunities* open to learners with SEN that supports their inclusion into wider society.

In the sections below, each of the descriptors relating to rights issues are considered. Using the information collected during the MIPIE project – both existing country data and indicators currently used, or proposed for use at international level (i.e. by the European Commission, OECD, Eurostat, Agency) – potential indicators necessary for mapping policy for the implementation of policy for inclusive education are identified.

As a result of an analysis of country data collection work, it is evident that information necessary to inform the learner – or person – level is most often incorporated within data collection activities conducted at the national/regional (macro), school (meso) or, most usually, classroom (micro) level. As such, possible indicators relating to these three levels of data collection are highlighted within this and the following chapter.

It is important to note that the tables presented in this and the following chapter do not indicate that data already exists, but rather that countries have indicated that quantitative or qualitative information that could lead to data or indicators in the longer term is currently available.

Information on current information available in countries has been analysed in relation to a number of key issues and is presented here and the next chapter.

Information available in countries is indicated with an X. The following notations are used in all tables to indicate the type of information available:

X – information available, but the type is unknown,

X (Qn) – information that could lead to quantitative data,

X (Ql) – information that could lead to qualitative data,

Fc – information is forthcoming,

EvN – information will eventually be available.

In addition, individual country notes and explanations are indicated by numbered table footnotes.

5.1 Indicators relating to participation in education and training

A core issue to be mapped in relation to the rights of learners with SEN is that of participation opportunities in education and training; the main focus being upon how far inclusive education policies foster equality in terms of access and ensure that learners with SEN are not excluded from any level of the general education system on the basis of their disability or special needs.

As indicated in the following table, drawing on information collected as part of the MIPIE project (and available in full from <http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mapping-the-implementation-of-policy-for-inclusive-education/country-data-collection-work>) most countries currently gather quantitative data indicating the numbers of learners with SEN enrolled in different types of settings.

Table 6: Country information currently available relating to learner enrolment

Countries/Patterns of admission	National level	Regional level	School level	Classroom level	Learner level
Austria	X (Qn)	X (Qn)			
Belgium (Fl)	X (Qn) (1)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Belgium (Fr)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Cyprus	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	
Czech Rep.	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Denmark	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Estonia	X (Qn)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn + Ql)
Finland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
France	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Germany	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Greece	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
Hungary	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Ql)
Iceland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
Ireland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Italy	X	X	X	X	X
Latvia	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		
Lithuania	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Luxembourg	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Malta	X (Qn)		X (Qn)	X (Ql)	
Netherlands	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		Evn
Norway	X	X	X	X	X
Poland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X(Qn + Ql)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Portugal	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Slovenia	X	X	X	X	X
Spain	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
Sweden			X (Qn)		
Switzerland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn + Ql Evn)
United Kingdom (England)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
United Kingdom (Scotland)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
United Kingdom (Wales)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)

Source: MIPIE Country data collection exercise

(1) 'National' level refers to data on the level of the Flemish Community

However, not all countries are able to provide reliable data on the inclusiveness of the education system. Whereas all countries are able to give reliable information on those learners enrolled in special schools, some of them face difficulties in having a precise picture of learners enrolled in different types of fully inclusive settings. For example, Belgium (French speaking community) only counts those learners who are 'newly

integrated' for a reference year in fully inclusive settings whereas Greece, Sweden or Switzerland do not collect data on learners with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes. Denmark does not collect data on all special needs learners enrolled in inclusive settings.

Information on learners with SEN enrolled in special, segregated classes in mainstream schools is also often imprecise. While some countries such as Belgium (Flemish speaking community) and Poland do not have special classes in mainstream schools, others, such as Germany, Hungary, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Portugal and Spain do not currently collect data on the numbers of learners in such classes.

5.1.1 Current and feasible quantitative indicators relating to participation

Existing information at country level indicates that it is possible to identify an indicator on participation rates of school age learners in mainstream education for national and European level data collection work. The indicator that is currently available from existing data focuses upon the *percentage of learners with SEN who are educated in segregated settings*. The operational definition of segregated education agreed upon by Agency member countries, is where a learner is formally identified in a country as having SEN and follows education in separate special classes or special schools for the largest part – 80% or more – of their school day.

Work within the MIPIE project suggests that data on learners with SEN in segregated settings is currently the most comparable across countries and that this quantitative data can be used in indicating certain trends in provision and movements towards inclusion.

However, the potential usefulness of any data on participation could be greatly improved by linking it to more systematic data collection at the classroom and/or learner level. It can be seen that policy relevant indicators would not only be comparable – both between countries and within longitudinal data collection work – but would focus on participation in inclusive settings, not segregated provision.

An approach focussed upon placement in segregated settings may be too restrictive to work within the paradigm shift underpinning developments towards inclusive education. Inclusive education is not only about enrolling learners with SEN in mainstream settings, but about ensuring that education policies and practices to meet the diversity of educational needs (UNESCO, 2009; Agency, 2011). In other words, it is about changing the education system so that it will be flexible enough to accommodate any learner and not about trying to change the learner so that he/she can fit more conveniently into a particular form of provision available within an unchanged education system.

Most importantly, in line with the arguments outlined above relating to rights and equity for all learners in education, future data collection should take an approach in line with inclusive education as an approach for all learners.

By examining data that might possibly be collected by countries, a feasible indicator could focus upon data relating to the *percentage of all learners of a certain age group (for instance 9 or 14 years old) that follow the mainstream curriculum with their peers of the same age for at least 80% of the time*. Data could be collected by all countries using an agreed approach: either collecting data for all learners of a particular age, or using a random sampling approach.

This indicator has a number of potential advantages: it would provide classroom level data to verify national or regional level data and would focus on all learners (not only those identified as having SEN) therefore emphasising inclusion, not segregation. In addition this indicator would:

- Provide learner level data that would permit breakdowns covering type of need, gender, etc.;
- Examine participation, but avoid labelling issues;
- Address many existing comparability issues identified in countries including 'labels' for particular types of provision (special classes, etc.) and problems related to learners who are outside education (as they would be included in the reference cohort);
- Be comparable between countries, in the short term and also taking a longitudinal approach;
- Focus essentially upon practice (i.e. actual participation) not on policies.

However, two main potential issues with this indicator are apparent: is such learner level data available and or collectable in all countries and is the detection of the basic reference cohort (i.e. all 9 year olds in a country) easily identifiable?

As a result of the MIPIE project work, it is argued that quantitative data collection in line with this proposed indicator is practicable and potentially useful and could be pursued at the European level in the near future.

5.1.2 The need for additional quantitative indicators in relation to participation

While it is argued that the current and feasible indicators discussed above would provide useful quantitative data, it is recognised that additional indicators are required if trends in provision and movement towards inclusion are to be fully understood. Such potential indicators would focus upon a number of critical areas:

- (i) From a quantitative point of view, further work is required on developing an indicator relating to transition from special schools to mainstream schools as well as transition from special, separate classes to mainstream classes.
- (ii) Further work could also focus on how far existing information provides clear data on learners with SEN who are out of school and more systematic data collection relating to this issue.
- (iii) It is also unclear how far existing information gives an accurate picture on participation opportunities across the levels of education that meet the requirements outlined in the UNCRPD to foster equal opportunities at all levels of education.

Indeed, data provided to the Agency as well as to other international agencies (OECD/CRELL, Eurydice) focuses almost exclusively upon school aged learners. Most data excludes pre-primary education, despite that fact that this level of provision has a clear impact on learners' opportunities for inclusion, on their educational achievement during compulsory schooling and on early school leaving (European Commission, 2009; WHO, 2011).

(iv) Current data tends to exclude those learners enrolled in upper secondary education and beyond despite its importance for learners' participation in work and society. Research clearly indicates that those learners who have completed upper secondary education are more likely to be included in society and to contribute to community and less likely to experience negative social experiences (Townsend et al., 2010; Bearman and Moody 2004; Crosnoe and Needham, 2004). Young adults with SEN in higher education have better employment opportunities, better chances to maintain their employability and tend to be more able to cope with transition periods linked to job opportunities (Ebersold, 2011; OECD, 2006; Eurostat, 2008).

(v) Current data collection systems do not identify if inclusive education policies ensure, as required by the UNCRPD, an inclusive education system at all levels. Many countries cannot breakdown their data by level of compulsory education and it is unclear how far data on pre-primary education and on post compulsory education, including lifelong learning opportunities exists at country level. According to both Eurybase and the information provided by countries within the MIPIE project, some have quantitative data on learners with SEN at different levels (pre-school level through to higher education), but it is unclear if all countries do so. It is also highly probable that differences in approaches to disability and data collection procedures raise comparability issues across levels of education.

5.1.3 The need for indicators exploring quality issues in relation to participation

Throughout all of the MIPIE project work it has been clearly recognised that quantitative data cannot provide any indication of the quality, suitability or appropriateness of education provided for learners with SEN. From a qualitative point of view, countries appear to lack information on admission issues, especially at school, classroom and at learner level. Discussions within the MIPIE project as well as an examination of findings and recommendations from Agency thematic work (2007, 2010, 2011) suggests that it is necessary to complement existing national and regional level information on policies, with qualitative data relating to:

- The existence of anti-discrimination legislation facilitating entrance to and participation in training, further and higher education;
- Procedures and resources for early identification and assessment of SEN;
- Funding models for schools that allow them to respond to the needs of all learners with minimal recourse to additional funding for specific needs;
- Policies for initial and further teacher education to include preparation for all teachers to work with diversity in inclusive settings.

At school level (information on practice), additional data collection would need to relate to:

- Policy statements including SEN issues and the existence of an action plan for inclusive education;
- Established rules for inclusive admission policies;
- Established rules for promoting an inclusive ethos and best inclusive practice;
- Teachers and other staff being supported to develop their knowledge, skills and attitudes regarding inclusion so they are prepared to meet all learners' needs in mainstream classrooms.

At classroom level, data collection would consider how teachers:

- Refer to and implement policies and guidelines for inclusive education;
- Are able to use flexible pedagogy to meet all needs;
- Plan, teach and review in partnership with their colleagues.

5.2 Indicators relating to access to support and accommodation

Access to support and accommodation is another core issue for monitoring rights issues and specifically the requirement to make the overall system inclusive as outlined in the UNCRPD. Article 24 requires State parties to deliver appropriate accommodation and data collection should be able to examine the type of additional resources allocated and their

ability to facilitate effective education from both a quantitative and a qualitative point of view.

It is unclear how many countries are able to provide data on additional resources allocated to learners with SEN. Many may gather qualitative information on additional resources through reports drafted by school inspectors, schools' quality control mechanisms or surveys. Some countries may have more quantitative information. France, Greece and Lithuania provide Eurybase information on the numbers of specialist teachers monitoring the specific curriculum of learners with SEN and/or the numbers of additional teachers or special educational support assistants.

Within the MIPIE project, France, Ireland, Slovenia, Switzerland and UK (Wales) indicated that they have data on resources allocated. Some have information on the numbers of learners with SEN benefiting from an assistant's support, while others have data on the number of personal assistant hours, or the number of hours provided for rehabilitation support, as well as for specific subjects (mathematics, foreign languages, etc.)

Overall, existing data on access to accommodation and support appears to be incomplete both from a qualitative and a quantitative point of view. Data does not show precisely if accommodation and support are available when needed or whether they are appropriate to a learner's needs. It may therefore be necessary to examine whether existing information allows the development of indicators regarding:

- The availability of support – describing the proportion of learners with SEN receiving additional resources in the form of support and accommodation;
- Individual needs that are not being met – presenting the proportion of learners with or without SEN receiving additional resources to enable them to fulfil the same tasks as their peers;
- Enabling effect of support – highlighting the proportion of learners receiving additional resources having the same success/progress opportunities as their non-SEN peers as a result of the support and arrangements;
- Key competences – describing the effectiveness of support to provide where appropriate learners with SEN with key competences acquired by their non-SEN peers;
- Learners' parental involvement – outlining parents' reporting on schools' effectiveness in ensuring their involvement in the educational process;
- Learners' involvement – outlining learners' perceptions of their schools' effectiveness in ensuring their involvement in the educational process.

Future work in countries would essentially develop both the quantitative and qualitative indicators proposed by the Agency in the report *Development of a set of indicators – for inclusive education in Europe*, as well as those proposed by other agencies, to examine at the national, school and classroom level existing: '*rules and processes to respect equal treatment of all pupils/learners without any exceptions*' (2009, p. 28).

5.3 Indicators relating to learning success and transition opportunities

Experts involved in the MIPIE project indicated clearly that monitoring the implementation of rights issues also requires a focus on the ability of education systems to enable learners with SEN to have the *same achievement opportunities* as their peers.

Whilst the 1997 ISCED classification relates special needs education to the education system's ability to '*stimulate efficient and effective learning for these pupils*', the 2011 ISCED definition focuses upon the ability of education systems to enable learners with

SEN to *'meet the learning objectives in an educational learning programme'* and emphasises educational opportunities beyond schooling.

Existing qualitative and quantitative data on outcome opportunities are limited and vary widely among countries. According to the information delivered within the MIPIE project, 22 out of 30 countries can provide some information on learners' outcomes at national level although some countries indicate that they have only information on those learners enrolled in special schools or in special classes in mainstream education.

Some of these countries have qualitative data that may be collected by researchers, or via evaluation and inspection reports, or reports from stakeholders involved in the implementation of individual education programmes (IEPs) or individual transition plans (ITPs) defined by the Agency as: *'a tool, in a form of a document in which the past, the present and the desired future of young people is documented.'* (2006, p. 21).

Table 7: Country information currently available relating to learning success and transition opportunities

Countries/Patterns	National level	Regional level	School level	Classroom level	Learner level
Austria					
Belgium (Fl)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Belgium (Fr)					
Cyprus	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	
Czech Republic	X (Ql)				
Denmark	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X	X (Qn)
Estonia	X	X	X		X
Finland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
France		X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Germany	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Greece	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc
Hungary	X (Ql)		X (Qn)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Iceland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Ireland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Italy					
Latvia	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		
Lithuania	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Luxembourg	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Malta	X (Ql)		X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Netherlands	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Norway					
Poland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Portugal	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X	X	X
Slovenia	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Spain					
Sweden					
Switzerland	X (Qn)				
United Kingdom (England)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
United Kingdom (Scotland)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
United Kingdom (Wales)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)

Source: MIPIE Country data collection exercise

As the table shows, most countries have quantitative information, although the type of information is very unclear. Many indicate that they are able to identify learners' levels of attainment and the grades or certificates awarded, but they can more rarely identify actual learning achievements. Some have outcome related data for learners in separate, special education settings while others are able to follow learners within the overall system.

Additional work may be required to clarify if existing data can be used to examine the education system's ability to promote equity and active participation for learners receiving additional resources. Potential indicators in this area would focus upon:

Graduation rates – describing the proportion of learners with SEN graduating with a 'regular diploma' compared to their non-SEN peers;

Drop out rates – that present the proportion of learners with SEN who have dropped out of different sectors of education compared to their non-SEN peers.

From a qualitative point of view, such data collection may lead to an investigation at national level to see if all learners receive at least a certificate describing his/her skills when schooling is finished and at school level whether established rules for assessment and recording focus upon and encourage the achievements of all learners, including those with SEN.

Monitoring learners' rights in education requires information to be gathered on the transition opportunities that learners with SEN have from one education level to another, or from education to the labour market. Experts involved in the MIPIE work indicated clearly that collecting data in relation to quality of education requires evidence relating to the whole context of a learners' environment, including longer-term outcomes of education and learners' destinations.

This means examining the gaps that learners may face during transition periods due to: new demands placed upon them by the education system; eligibility criteria and procedures for support and accommodation and new responsibilities they may have to assume. These gaps may have a disabling effect by overexposing learners with SEN to segregated settings, unemployment and to exclusion (Agency, 2006; Ebersold, 2011).

Drawing on information provided within this project, nine countries out of 30 have information on learners' transition opportunities and one country has plans to collect such information. Some countries have qualitative data collected within ITPs, but most have quantitative data only. Countries that provide data on transition opportunities are: Belgium (Flemish speaking community); Cyprus; Finland; Iceland; Ireland; Lithuania; Malta; Netherlands; Portugal; United Kingdom (England, Scotland and Wales).

This data may identify destination after leaving special schools and/or mainstream schools and/or follow school careers. Some countries follow learners between primary and secondary education, whereas others follow the transition between lower secondary education and upper secondary education. Some countries have information on learners going through the transition process.

Overall, a real data gap seems to exist on transition issues, although more and more countries do include the transition issue in both their education and their inclusive education policies in line with the Salamanca Framework for Action which states that schools should support learners with SEN to make an effective transition from school to adult working life (UNESCO, 1994; Agency, 2006; Ebersold, 2011).

As research has demonstrated the importance of individual transition plans in effective and coherent transition from education to work or from secondary education to tertiary education, future quantitative indicators at the national level could consider the presence of ITPs linked to learners' IEPs, as well as the existence of transition support services.

From a qualitative point of view, building on previous work done by the Agency as well as the OECD may lead to a focus upon how supportive methods of funding are on this issue, on the development of integrated transition systems, on the existence of longitudinal studies, or on existing procedures for access, continuing attendance and progress of all

learners in all stages of education (preschool, compulsory education, higher and continuing education (Agency, 2011, Ebersold, 2011).

At school level, indicators could focus on the availability of transition support services, their appropriateness to individuals' needs and their enabling effect in terms, for example, of needs awareness, ability to make decisions on plans for the future, self-confidence in decision making and the ability to match individual strengths and desires with future goals.

5.4 Indicators relating to affiliation opportunities

Monitoring rights issues requires a focus upon the affiliation opportunities that learners have throughout their education. The UNCRPD makes clear that inclusive education is about acceptance and belonging as well as effectively participating in society beyond schooling.

Any comprehensive attempt to map the implementation of policy for inclusive education must therefore include data on the degree of empowerment that learners acquire through their education to make decisions affecting their lives, to assume responsibilities and to actively participate in society (OECD/Ebersold, 2011).

At national level, such data collection could usefully build upon the indicators used by CRELL (2009) to measure social and civic competences and include for example, the composite indicator on civic competences as well as the one on active citizenship (actions) of adults. This would require learners with SEN to be included in the International Civic and Citizenship Education study (ICCS – see: http://www.iea.nl/fileadmin/user_upload/Publications/Electronic_versions/ICCS_2009_International_Report.pdf).

These composite indicators could be complemented by qualitative indicators examining the extent to which learners with SEN feel prepared by schools for:

- Civic engagement;
- Meaningful employment;
- Being financially self-supportive;
- Active participation in society;
- Engaging in entrepreneurship;
- Independent living.

Data collection could also take into account individuals' sense of belonging and look at the education system's ability to enable learners with SEN to enjoy a good quality of life and engage in reciprocal friendships, as well as wider community involvement (Flahaut, 2002, Fraser, 2005, Ebersold, 2007).

Chapter 5 summary

The first of two essential content areas that need to be incorporated within the mapping framework is that of monitoring learners' rights. Future data collection must be in line with the UNCRPD 2006, as this increasingly has an influence upon countries' legal frameworks for education. Mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education therefore requires indicators providing evidence of the ability of education systems to be equitable for learners with SEN.

It is possible to identify key rights issues to correspond with the different phases of the input, process, output/outcomes model. A descriptor can then be identified in relation to each of these key rights issues, with each descriptor including different indicators. These descriptors correspond to areas of data collection work that are already in evidence in countries to a greater or lesser extent.

Input can be seen to correspond to equity of access for learners with SEN in terms of their participation in education in non-segregated settings; process to equity in relation to educational opportunities for learners with SEN and the possibilities within the system to provide them with appropriate support to meet their needs; outputs to equity in terms of achievement opportunities and possibilities for academic and social learning success and transition opportunities open to learners with SEN; outcomes to equity in relation to personal autonomy during and after formal education and in particular the affiliation opportunities open to learners with SEN that support their inclusion into wider society.

Looking across the quantitative and qualitative information currently collected by countries participating in the MIPIE project, potential areas for indicators can be identified for:

- Participation in education and training;
- Access to support and accommodation;
- Learning success and transition opportunities;
- Affiliation opportunities.

Currently, the existing information at country level indicates that it is possible to identify an indicator on participation rates of school age learners in mainstream education for national and European level data collection work. However, an approach focussed upon placement in segregated settings may be too restrictive to work within the paradigm shift underpinning developments towards inclusive education. Inclusive education is not only about enrolling learners with SEN in mainstream settings, but about ensuring that education policies and practices to meet the diversity of educational needs.

It can be seen that policy relevant indicators would not only be comparable – both between countries and within longitudinal data collection work – but would focus upon focus on participation in inclusive settings, not segregated provision. Most importantly, in line with the arguments outlined above relating to rights and equity for all learners in education, future data collection should be in line with inclusive education as an approach for all learners.

By examining data that might possibly be collected by countries, a feasible indicator could focus upon data relating to the *percentage of all learners of a certain age group (for instance 9 or 14 years old) that follow the mainstream curriculum with their peers of the same age for at least 80% of the time*. Data could be collected by all countries using an agreed approach: either collecting data for all learners of a particular age, or using a random sampling approach.

This indicator has a number of potential advantages: it would provide classroom level data to verify national or regional level data and would focus on all learners (not only those identified as having SEN) therefore emphasising inclusion, not segregation.

6. MONITORING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SYSTEMS FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The previous chapter discussed the use of the proposed framework for data gathering and focused on the first of two essential content areas – that of monitoring learners’ rights. This chapter considers the second essential area: that of monitoring the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education.

The availability of data on the performance and progress of education systems was a main priority identified by policy makers participating in the MIPIE project and it was argued that data collection should provide information on inclusive settings, as well as on special schools and special classes.

The MIPIE project experts agreed that it would be ideal to have evidence that learners’ rights and needs are being met by examining data relating to the effectiveness of initial assessment procedures, to the on-going involvement of learners and their families in educational experiences and to the effectiveness of learning environments in overcoming barriers and supporting meaningful learning experiences for all learners. They also emphasised that data should, as far as possible, be comparable with the UOE questionnaire and data collection procedures.

They further agreed that at national level data should:

- Facilitate planning and the monitoring of resources and personnel;
- Determine the effectiveness of teacher education;
- Evaluate cost effectiveness.

At school level, data collection should:

- Provide information that helps teachers and school staff to plan and deliver appropriate support and provision;
- Give clear insights into how parents and learners are enabled to be a full part of the educational process.

This chapter relates investments made in inclusive education (input) to performance (process of education). Specifically, it looks at gathering data on the ability of education systems to ‘perform well’ – that is to achieve desired results without wasting resources, effort, time or money – in order to empower learners with SEN. Using the model developed in previous chapters, the issues and descriptors linked to the input and process phases of the model are presented in the table below.

Table 8: Issues and descriptors relating to effectiveness

Key issues corresponding to effectiveness	Input		Process of education							
	Cost-effectiveness		Receptiveness to diversity		Quality of learning		Quality of support		Teacher effectiveness	
Descriptors corresponding to effectiveness	Resource allocation		Admission		Assessment		Planning		Teaching	
Indicators	Qn	QI	Qn	QI	Qn	QI	Qn	QI	Qn	QI
National/regional level										
School level										
Classroom level										
Learner level										

Qn – Quantitative QI – Qualitative

In terms of examining the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education, the model relates *input* to the key issue of *cost effectiveness*, with the corresponding descriptor focussing upon *resource allocation*. The possible data collection relating to this issue is discussed in the next section.

The *process of education* is related to four key issues: *receptiveness to diversity*, *quality of learning*, *quality of support* and *teacher effectiveness*. Each of these issues is linked with a corresponding descriptor: *admission*, *assessment*, *planning* and *teaching*.

However, it is not possible to understand the quality of complex policies and practice via data collection linked to one or two indicators. Cost-effectiveness in terms of short and long-term outcomes for learners must include debates about the value of wider as well as academic learning. Information provided by countries on the implementation of the process of inclusive education suggests that data collection may necessitate specific studies using a variety of indicators focussing upon specific issues. The later sections of this chapter therefore propose a range of possible indicators for data collection relating to each descriptor – admission, assessment, planning and teaching – covering quantitative and qualitative indicators relating to national/regional, school, classroom and learner levels of education.

As with the previous chapter, examples of indicators that may be used for analysing issues are proposed, based upon information provided by countries within the MIPIE project, existing indicators used by international organisations (OECD, UNESCO, Agency), as well as research work conducted at the international and/or national levels. As with the previous chapter, possible indicators for future data collection are identified in relation to national, school and classroom level data as it is considered that data collected within these three levels informs the learner level.

6.1 Indicators relating to resource allocation

The effectiveness of inclusive education depends upon the financial, technical and human resources invested by countries for the education of learners with SEN. Within the MIPIE project work, policy makers agreed that data collection should provide information about investments made for additional resources – human and technical – allocated to learners and schools; data should also be collected on the ability of these resources to empower learners with SEN and the professionals who work with them. Specifically, three areas for data collection relating to resource allocation can be highlighted:

- General expenditure;
- Expenditure relating to teachers;
- Expenditure relating to research.

Each of these is discussed in the paragraphs below.

In the 2011 enquiry into special needs education, Eurostat has proposed that data gathering work could focus upon expenditure on special needs education potentially covering expenditure on: SNE education in public and private institutions; capital investment; teachers with SNE qualifications; additional teachers supporting both learners and teachers as well as on non-teaching staff. Data collection could lead to a breakdown of expenditure by type of settings, level of source of funding (national, regional, local) and type of ministry (education, health) (Eurostat, <http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/mapping-the-implementation-of-policy-for-inclusive-education/budapest-conference-/Lene-Mejer-and-Thierry-Huart.pdf>).

However, despite the requests for data on expenditure linked to resource allocation, within the MIPIE country data collection exercise, most countries did not provide information on the availability of data on spending and investment, or on potential breakdowns. A few countries already collect data on budgets in their national data collection systems, but further work needs to be done to explore the possible aggregation of data on funding provided by different ministries for the education of learners with SEN, and on including private funding in data collection.

Policy makers also suggested that data collection should include information on the effectiveness of initial and in-service teacher education, particularly on its ability to prepare staff to implement inclusive education. This request is supported by the findings from the teaching and learning international survey (TALIS) developed by the OECD (2009) which shows that most teachers do not feel prepared to cope with diversity in their classrooms following initial and in-service teacher education. Data collection relating to expenditure on teachers could, in addition to considering teacher-learner ratios, also include expenditure on inclusive teacher education, its enabling effects for learners and how teachers are supported to feel able to cope with diversity issues in their classroom.

Countries collect only limited information on teacher investment issues and existing data is mainly qualitative, resulting from qualitative research or inspection reports. Within the MIPIE survey, no countries provided information on the budget allocated to the training of teaching and non-teaching staff on inclusive education. Some countries indicate that they have information on the number of teachers who provide special education, while others said that they have data on teachers working in special classes. A third group of countries have data on non-teaching staff involved in inclusive and special education.

The Eurydice database (http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/education/eurydice/eurybase_en.php) relating to special needs education shows how data may vary among countries. In the national descriptions, 12 countries have data on teaching staff. Of these, 6 have data exclusively on teaching staff enrolled in special schools. In addition, 4 countries indicate the number of non-teaching staff involved in the education of learners with SEN and 3 countries specify a teacher/learner ratio.

In summary, data on teachers and investment on teaching issues is an area for further work in all countries. The TALIS survey could be a useful tool in gathering data on teachers' ability to work with learners with SEN, but further work needs to be done.

MIPIE project policy makers and data collection experts suggested that data collection should examine the investment made by countries in research on inclusive education. Detailed research – particularly on the effectiveness of different approaches – is considered a key area for promoting inclusive education as well as for monitoring both the implementation of the right to education and the performance of the inclusive education system. One potential area for future data collection would be an examination of investments in research on inclusive education, as a percentage of investments made in research on education generally. However, virtually no information on this issue was provided via the project country data collection exercise and so it is argued that this is an area for future attention and development.

Data relating to general teacher and research expenditures would mainly be quantitative in nature and would be collected at the national and regional level. As such, the data collection could be supplemented with qualitative school level information relating to the existence of:

- Accountability systems considering the enabling effect of policies and practices;
- Resources allocated for staff development;

- Resources allocated for parental and learner involvement;
- Guidelines for promoting best inclusive education practices.

6.2 Indicators relating to admission

Admission policies and practices play a key role in the quality of inclusive education. They can support the transition process, reduce barriers to attendance and empower learners to be involved in their school community (Agency, 2006, OECD, 2009, Ebersold, 2011). The MIPIE project experts agreed that data collection on school admission policies is a necessary element of considering wider system effectiveness issues.

Only limited quantitative and qualitative data on admission policies is currently collected in countries, but proposals for future data collection in this area can be made based upon the experts discussion as well as a consideration of research in this area. From a quantitative point of view, school level data collection could include the percentage of learners who:

- Were satisfied with their transition to school;
- Felt supported to disclose information about their needs;
- Felt well informed about educational opportunities and support;
- Felt welcome in their schools.

For learners with more complex and profound needs, their families or advocates could be asked to provide this information on their behalf.

From a qualitative point of view, national or regional data collection in relation to admission could encompass:

- Existing laws and rules requiring schools to develop accessible admission policies and strategies;
- The existence of good practice guides for admission;
- The existence of established laws and/or policies requiring schools to support transition to their facilities.

At school level, data collection could consider the factors that impact upon the quality of schools' admission strategies. Building upon previous work on admission issues (OECD, 2009, Ebersold, 2011), these criteria appear to be important for data collection:

- The existence of non-discriminatory admission rules and policies supporting inclusive cultures and promoting inclusive values;
- Policies and strategies developed to support learners in disclosing their needs and the impact that they have on learners;
- The existence of a clear policy statement against bullying;
- The implementation of existing codes of practice on inclusive education by the school management team;
- The existence of staff training sessions on admission issues and on creating a welcoming school climate, working respectfully and collaboratively with learners and families;
- Strategies developed to help learners and families to participate actively in the school community and classroom;
- The availability of information, counselling and advice strategies and their impact on learners.

School level information would need to be supplemented by data from the classroom level, which could, for example, include strategies adopted by teachers to welcome learners and information on teachers' understanding of learner difference and diverse needs.

6.3 Indicators relating to assessment

Work completed previously by Agency member countries suggests that they understand assessment as determinations and judgments made about individuals (or sometimes small groups) based on some form of evidence. Watkins (2007) defines assessment as: *'the ways teachers and other people involved in a pupil's education systematically collect and then use information about that pupil's level of achievement and/or development in different areas of their educational experience (academic, behaviour and social)'*. (p. 14).

According to this definition, assessment differs clearly from evaluation that refers to: *'the examination of non-person centred factors such as organisation, curricula and teaching methods'* (ibid).

Many countries have information on assessment issues at national level and in most cases this information is quantitative. According to the country data collection exercise, 21 out of 30 countries have data on assessment at national level, 17 at regional level, 16 at school level, 13 at classroom level and 15 at learner level. In some countries, data collected at national level aims mainly to inform policies; data gathered at regional level targets strategic planning and provision and data collected at school and classroom level is used to support stakeholders in delivering support to learners.

At national level or regional level, some countries have data on learners' academic and social achievements while others indicate enrolment rates by placement, or type of SEN. A third group of countries have data on learners assessed either for recommended support or according to an educational need.

While most countries have quantitative data at national and regional level, some have qualitative data at school, classroom or learner level. They provide information on the number of learners referred, on the nature of assessment and on the support and/or provision recommended. Information may result from material recorded within a learner's individual education programme (IEP) or within diagnostic tests used to identify learners' needs.

Table 9: Country information currently available relating to assessment

Countries/Patterns	Assessment at national level	Assessment at regional level	Assessment at School level	Assessment at Classroom level	Assessment at Learner level
Austria	X	X			
Belgium (Fl)	X (Qn)		Fc		X
Belgium (Fr)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)	X (Qn)	(Qn)
Cyprus	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	
Czech Republic					
Denmark		X	X	X	X
Estonia	X (Qn)	X (Qn)			X (Qn + Ql)
Finland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
France	X (Qn)	X	X	X	X
Germany	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Greece	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc
Hungary	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Ql)
Iceland	X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X	X	X
Ireland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Italy	X	X			
Latvia	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		

Lithuania	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Ql)
Luxembourg				X	
Malta	X (Qn + Ql)		X (Qn)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Netherlands	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		Evn
Norway	X	X	X	X	X
Poland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn + Ql)
Portugal	X	X	X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X
Slovenia	X	X	X	X	X
Spain	X (Qn)	X (Qn)			
Sweden					
Switzerland	Fc				Evn
United Kingdom (England)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)			X
United Kingdom (Scotland)			X (Ql)		
United Kingdom (Wales)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)

Source: MIPIE Country data collection exercise

However, information provided by countries suggests that existing data does not allow an examination of assessment issues that clearly impact upon a system's effectiveness and two purposes of assessment within national policies identified by the Agency could be considered in future data collection work: assessment of educational needs and assessment to inform teaching and learning. Each of these is discussed below.

6.3.1 Assessment of educational needs

Assessment of educational needs plays a key role in the planning of the educational process, as well as in delivering appropriate education. Initial needs identification is, in many countries, used as the basis for identifying any additional resources for which learners may be eligible and may also be used as a starting point for the development of an IEP. Depending on the quality of the information provided on learners' educational needs, assessment information may or may not empower stakeholders to deliver appropriate support and effectively adapt their teaching to individuals' needs.

By considering the responses of country experts during the project as well as examining available research work in this area, it is proposed that, from a quantitative point of view, future data collection in this area could focus upon:

- Rates of learners receiving additional resources following a needs assessment related to curriculum goals. For example, the longitudinal study implemented within the OECD project *Pathways for students with disabilities to tertiary education and to employment* reveals that only one third of SEN students receiving additional resources in upper secondary education indicate that they had their educational need assessed in school year 2006/2007;
- Rates of teachers who feel empowered to effectively support learners;
- Rates of learners who report that their school facilitated learner and parent involvement;
- Rates of learners who were assessed and their eligibility for support identified within a certain time frame.

From a qualitative point of view, data collection on assessment of educational needs could include:

- Existing rules and guidelines for initial assessment, focussing upon learning and teaching practice that promotes inclusion in a mainstream setting;

- The existence of policies that promote inclusive assessment practice, taking into account the needs of all vulnerable learners including those with SEN;
- The existence of good practice guidelines on assessment of educational needs.

At school level, data collection would highlight whether assessment methods and strategies:

- Empower teachers to support learning;
- Actively involve learners and families;
- Are linked to curriculum goals;
- Are connected to an IEP;
- Are implemented systematically and accurately according to individuals' needs;
- Involve multi-disciplinary teams.

6.3.2 Assessment to inform teaching and learning

The use of assessment to inform teaching and learning, as well as to compare learners' achievements is recognised as having an impact on the implementation of effective inclusive education (Agency, 2009). The quality of such assessment procedures impacts on:

- The chances learners with SEN have to be as successful in education as their non-SEN peers;
- Teachers' ability to adapt their teaching practice to learners' needs and to plan the next steps in learning.

From a quantitative point of view, future data collection could focus upon:

- Rates of teachers feeling appropriately supported by assessment methods and tools;
- Rates of learners estimating how well assessment methods are adapted to their needs;
- Participation and performance of learners with SEN during assessments.

From a qualitative point a view, previous work suggests that data collection at national level could focus upon:

- Existing legislation ensuring that learners with SEN are entitled to take part in national and international assessments and examinations;
- Existing policies promoting the use of on-going assessment for learning in mainstream classes as well as in special classes and schools;
- The existence of policies promoting inclusive assessment practice, taking into account the needs of all vulnerable learners including those with SEN;
- The existence of good practice guidelines on assessment.

At school level, data collection could examine:

- Established rules for using national assessment information to inform educational planning for individual learners, as well as for school improvement;
- Statements relating to on-going assessment in school development plans;
- Co-operation policies developing multi-disciplinary teams to contribute to on-going assessment in mainstream classrooms;
- Assessment methods covering more than just academic/subject based content;

- How and when assessment results inform changes in learners' IEPs;
- Possibilities for developing the range of assessment methods and tools available to teachers;
- The participation of all learners in inclusive assessment.

6.4 Indicators relating to planning

Planning is a core dimension of the educational process and an understanding of planning issues is essential in order to explore the effectiveness of systems of inclusive education. Planning activities build upon the identification of learners' needs to define all the necessary aspects of the teaching and learning process. Information currently collected by countries in relation to planning issues is presented in the table below.

Table 10: Country information currently available relating to planning

Countries/Patterns	Planning at national level	Planning at regional level	Planning at School level	Planning at Classroom level	Planning at Learner level
Austria	X	X			
Belgium (Fl)	X (Ql)		X (Ql)		X (Ql)
Belgium (Fr)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		X (Qn)
Cyprus	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	
Czech Republic	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)
Denmark		X	X	X	X
Estonia	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Finland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		X (Qn)
France	X	X	X	X	X
Germany				X	
Greece	X (Qn)	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc
Hungary	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Iceland		X	X (Ql)		X (Ql)
Ireland					
Italy					
Latvia			X (Qn)		
Lithuania			Evn – Ql	Evn – Ql	Evn – Ql
Luxembourg					
Malta				X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Netherlands					X (Ql)
Norway	X	X	X	X	X
Poland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Portugal			X (Qn +Ql)	X (Qn +Ql)	X (Ql)
Slovenia	X	X	X	X	X
Spain					
Sweden					
Switzerland	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc
United Kingdom (England)	X (Qn)				
United Kingdom (Scotland)			X (Ql)		
United Kingdom (Wales)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)

Source: MIPIE Country data collection exercise

14 out of 30 countries indicated they have information on planning issues at national level and that data is mainly quantitative. Some countries indicate that they have data on learner enrolment by type of setting, while others count the number of IEPs or the number of statements within the annual review of all statements. Some countries also indicate that they are able to report on the level of support provided to learners, while others have information on adapted syllabi.

13 out of 30 countries have data – mainly quantitative – at regional/local level. In many cases, existing information at national level can be disaggregated by regional/local level except when data corresponds to information collected by local authorities responsible for allocation of resources.

18 out of 30 countries have quantitative and/or qualitative data at school level that is provided by reports, external or internal evaluation of schools and via school plans and/or IEPs implemented by schools. In addition, 14 out of 30 countries have mainly qualitative data at classroom level and 16 have data at learner level.

However, existing data does not appear to allow an analysis of planning policies and practice according to existing quality criteria and there is a clear need for both quantitative and qualitative indicators on this issue.

From a quantitative point of view, data collection could be linked to two indicators on the implementation of IEPs that are key planning tools for high quality inclusive education policies and practices. These indicators are:

- *Rates of school aged learners receiving additional resources as specified within an IEP* in order to identify if support and arrangements are framed within a coherent plan. For example, the longitudinal study implemented within the OECD project *Pathways for learners with disabilities to tertiary education and to employment* (2011) reveals that only one fifth of learners with SEN receiving additional resources in upper secondary education declare that supports and arrangements are framed within an IEP.

- *Rates of 15 years old learners receiving additional resources whose IEPs include an ITP* examining the number of learners involved in planning their future at an early stage in their schooling. This is a crucial issue raised within *Individual Transition Plans – supporting the move from school to employment* (Agency, 2006) report.

Building upon previous work exploring planning issues, future data collection at national level could include:

- Appropriate on going assessment methods are used to monitor and update IEP targets;
- Requirements made on schools to develop action plans for inclusive education;
- Data collected on school completion rates and post-school outcomes being used to plan improvements in educational programmes and services.

At school level, data collection on planning should consider the rules and procedures that are established in relation to:

- Connecting planning with learners' needs and objectives defined within their IEPs;
- IEP objectives being cross-curricular and integral to all classroom practice;
- Including, where appropriate, transition issues in IEPs;
- The involvement of learners' and parents including dissemination of information to them;
- Evaluating the quality and implementation of IEPs;
- Implementing multi-disciplinary approaches;
- Supporting collaborative planning and learning.

At classroom level, data collection would need to consider the following in relation to teachers' work:

- Implementing objectives documented in an IEP;
- Planning, teaching and reviewing work in partnership with others.

6.5 Indicators relating to teaching

Teacher effectiveness issues are critical in considering the effectiveness of the overall system for inclusive education. The information provided by countries within the MIPIE project indicates that current data does not permit an analysis of teaching practices, however, some countries indicate that they are planning to examine the quality of teaching and the teaching methods used in the future.

Table 11: Country information currently available relating to teaching

Countries/Patterns	National level	Regional level	School level	Classroom level	Learner level
Austria					
Belgium (Fl)	X (Ql)		X (Ql)		
Belgium (Fr)					
Cyprus		X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)	
Czech Republic	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
Denmark		X	X	X	X
Estonia	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn)			X (Ql)
Finland	X ((Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)		
France	X	X	X	X	X
Germany	X				
Greece	X (Qn)	Fc	Fc	Fc	Fc
Hungary	X (Qn + Ql)		X (Ql)	X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Iceland	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	
Ireland	X		X		
Italy	X	X			
Latvia					
Lithuania	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Ql)	
Luxembourg					
Malta				X (Ql)	X (Ql)
Netherlands	X (Qn)		X (Qn)		
Norway	X	X	X	X	X
Poland			X (Ql)	X (Ql)	
Portugal			X (Qn + Ql)	X (Qn + Ql)	X (Ql)
Slovenia	x	X	X	X	X
Spain	X (Qn)	X (Qn)			
Sweden					
Switzerland	X (Qn)				
United Kingdom (England)	X (Qn)				X (Ql)
United Kingdom (Scotland)			X (Qn)		
United Kingdom (Wales)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)	X (Qn)

Source: MIPIE Country data collection exercise

Only 18 out of 30 countries stated that they have information on teaching at national level. Existing quantitative data mainly identifies the number of teachers providing special education, or the number of specialists supporting teachers in their classrooms, but does not describe teaching practices. Some countries indicated they have qualitative information provided by inspection reports, research, external or internal evaluations.

Mapping the implementation of inclusive education policies requires the development of both quantitative and qualitative indicators that explore the teaching practices used with learners with SEN. Such indicators could usefully build upon those used to analyse teaching practices within the OECD TALIS (2009) survey to look at: teachers' beliefs; classroom teaching practices; co-operation among staff; class environment/class climate and school climate.

Data collection could also potentially build upon the OECD PISA (2007) questions on learners' perception of schools and on effective learning behaviours such as: beliefs, anxiety/emotional factors; learning strategies and motivation/attitudes.

Data collection relating to teaching could also examine school management factors that impact upon teaching, such as:

- Disability awareness policies and strategies;
- Opportunities for flexibility in the curriculum and for curricula to be related to real life needs and not only to academic learning;
- Policies and strategies regarding teaching for active participation in society;
- Policies and strategies on using difference as a resource for learning and teaching.

At classroom level, data collection would most usefully focus upon learners' experiences, namely:

- Active participation of all learners;
- Involving learners in decision making about their own learning;
- Opportunities for learning collaboratively and helping each other to learn.

Chapter 6 summary

Within the proposed framework for data gathering, the second essential content area is that of examining the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education. MIPIE project experts argue that it would be ideal to have evidence that learners' needs are being met by examining data relating to the effectiveness of initial assessment procedures, to the on-going involvement of learners and their families in educational experiences and the effectiveness of learning environments in overcoming barriers and supporting meaningful learning experiences for all learners.

They also emphasised that data should as far as possible be comparable with the UOE questionnaire and data collection procedures.

At national level data should:

- Facilitate planning and the monitoring of resources and personnel;
- Determine the effectiveness of teacher education;
- Evaluate the cost effectiveness of inclusive education systems.

At school level, data collection should:

- Provide information that supports teachers and school staff to plan and deliver appropriate support and provision;
- Give clear insights into how parents and learners are enabled to take a full part in the educational process.

In terms of examining the effectiveness of systems for inclusive education, the model proposed relates input to the key issue of cost effectiveness, with the corresponding descriptor focussing upon resource allocation.

The process of education is related to four key issues and corresponding descriptors:

- 1 - Receptiveness to diversity, as evidenced via admission data;
- 2 - Quality of learning, as evidenced via data on assessment;
- 3 - Quality of support, as evidenced via data on planning;
- 4 - Teacher effectiveness, as evidenced via data on teaching.

7. A PROPOSED AGENDA FOR EUROPEAN LEVEL DATA COLLECTION

This final chapter considers all of the proposals made during the MIPIE project, reported in this document and proposes an agenda for future developments in quantitative and qualitative data collection at the European level. The proposed agenda describes the issues to be considered and tasks to be implemented in order to achieve a synergy of efforts in data collection at the European and national levels.

7.1 A European agenda as a long-term strategy

At the European level, data collection work requires a short, mid and long-term strategy.

In the *short term*, the data collection strategy should be based upon the current Eurostat enquiry into quantitative data collection for special needs education and should carefully explore useful data within existing datasets. The resulting quantitative data collection work relating to inclusive education would be limited to collecting data that is required for comparative purposes at the European level and would cover a limited number of core quantitative indicators, primarily identified by the Eurostat enquiry, but also potentially incorporating those identified in section 5.1.1.

MIPIE project experts suggest that an agreed European approach would need to avoid the risk of only focussing on financial aspects of data collection. Most importantly, this approach would have to overcome outstanding issues regarding the interpretation of internationally agreed definitions of key concepts at national levels. Therefore, in the *mid-term*, a European data collection strategy would focus upon the implementation of article 24 of the UNCRRPD and investigate precisely which key information and data may be required, examine whether such data exists and clarify what work is required to gather the data that may be additionally needed.

However, in the *long-term*, a data collection strategy should follow a clearly agreed agenda with countries working within a shared framework. MIPIE project experts argued for a comprehensive set of data collection agreements covering concepts, definitions and methods that could be implemented at the national level as a 'minimum' for countries' data collection work.

In addition to a 'shared language' for data collection relating to inclusive education based on shared understandings of key concepts at the European level, a shared framework for mapping inclusive education would consider input, process, outputs and outcomes of the education system and provide quantitative and qualitative data collection relating to the system, school, classroom and learner levels.

This agenda would be based on the premise that inclusive education is a quality imperative and it would work to provide countries with quantitative and qualitative insights into the effectiveness of inclusive education policy and the quality of inclusive education practice. However, four areas of agreement need to be reached across countries in order to support European level work. These are outlined below.

7.1.1 Identify evidence required at national and at international level

A long term agenda for data collection at the European level would focus both on rights and effectiveness issues as described within the MIPIE project, as well as clarify which descriptors and indicators countries need to work on in order to have the evidence required for mapping activities at national and at European level.

The MIPIE project reveals that work needs to be done in order for countries to:

- Manage the monitoring requirements of article 24 of the UNCRC from a quantitative and qualitative perspective, but crucially foster inclusive education systems at all levels of education;
- Monitor the ability of education systems to ensure that learners' rights are met and that they experience equity in terms of access, participation, achievements and transition;
- Gain insights into the ability of education systems to prepare learners with SEN for active citizenship and inclusion into society.

In summary, all countries participating in the MIPIE project indicate that they face difficulties in analysing the effectiveness and cost effectiveness of their inclusive education system. They need to carry out substantial work on this issue at national level in order to have the evidence they require and potentially share this information with relevant international organisations.

7.1.2 Identify the most effective data available and data needing to be developed

MIPIE project experts agreed upon the need to re-think country data collection, in particular relating to:

- information about and from individuals rather than systems;
- School level data that involves the school, multi-disciplinary teams and parents;
- A reinterpretation of what is understood by 'learning outcomes', potentially incorporating information on how learners themselves define successful outcomes.

The MIPIE project has shown that currently the most feasible focus for data collection is learner enrolment in mainstream or segregated settings, although further work needs to be done in order to provide truly comparable data and breakdowns (covering type of need, gender, age, etc.).

In many cases, data on implementing inclusive education in countries is qualitative and small scale, especially in relation to analysing outcomes and outputs. It is unclear if existing qualitative information provides an understanding of the mechanisms impacting on achievement opportunities for learners with SEN, or how data may be compared at European level.

Information provided by countries within the MIPIE project does not give a clear picture of how existing data might be used to analyse the quality of the educational process in terms of admission, assessment, planning and teaching and these factors would be a key focus of future work.

7.1.3 Define coherent data gathering procedures and mechanisms at European and at national level

MIPIE project experts suggested that a European agenda for mapping the implementation of inclusive education needs to identify and clearly describe the diverse data collection procedures that may be required. Data that maps the relevant issues in relation to inclusive education must cover all sectors of the education system – preschool through to post compulsory, public and privately funded education, mainstream and segregated provision. Data collection procedures relevant to inclusive education must be embedded within all educational data gathering work.

However, as described in the previous chapters, not all of the required data can be collected on a quantitative basis from – for example – national statistical offices, annual surveys, or a learner census.

Country reviews may support policy makers to improve the quality of their inclusive education policies by providing a framework to compare experiences and examine 'best' or innovative practice relating to various aspects impacting on the quality and the effectiveness of inclusive education systems. Such reviews would include or at least draw upon longitudinal studies that provide an accurate picture of individuals' educational pathways within the education system as well as from the education system to the labour market. This would require countries to develop specific methodologies and data gathering procedures.

Supporting stakeholders in different ways to improve their inclusive education practice also requires information gathered through research and survey based approaches. Exploring assessment procedures and/or teaching practice may require the collection of case studies to provide evidence on the rationale underlying strategies developed, as well the attitudes, knowledge and skills required by different stakeholders to create supportive learning environments.

7.1.4 Address comparability issues

The MIPIE project reveals that comparability issues in relation to quantitative data are only partly addressed at the European level and the difficulties in analysis that may exist result from uncertainty in defining the target group at national, European and international levels. In addition, differences in the methodologies used for collecting data among countries reduce the use that can be made of national level data at European or international levels.

Countries should therefore consider how comparability issues relating to the purpose of data collection, analytical methods used and data collection processes (Lee and Mossaad, 2010) can be addressed so that national data collection can be aligned for European level purposes.

7.2 Developing synergy at national level

Country representatives in the MIPIE project were clear that mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education should consider and use all data collected at the national levels by Ministries of education as well as Ministries of health and welfare. Any country data collection needs to build on existing systems and not introduce additional or separate systems that may not be consistent with the principles of inclusive education.

Experts highlighted the need for synergies at national level between key stakeholders that would be based upon a clear rationale for data collection considering national, regional, school and classroom level data if country data is to effectively reflect practice. Such synergies require:

- A political will to include inclusive and special education issues in general data collection, as well as gathering specific data on learners with SEN;
- Improvement of inter-ministerial co-operation and multi-disciplinary approaches to data collection permitting connections between diverse data sets;
- Framing the data collection issue within a process of mutual learning for organisations working in the area in order to support and streamline requests for national level information;
- Inclusive education, disability and special educational needs to be perceived as key issues for all schools and service providers to account for in their data and information gathering. This involves encouraging key stakeholders to include questions focussing upon inclusive and special education issues in existing data collection surveys; supporting schools to collect data and work together in existing information collection programmes.

7.3 Developing synergy at European level

The MIPIE project clearly shows that although data is currently collected by various stakeholders at the international level, it does not have the appropriate type of information, the reliability or the coherence needed to provide countries with consistent messages on key issues and developments related to inclusive education.

The MIPIE project experts argued that any data collection for European level must:

- Clearly build upon existing national level data collection;
- Directly link to the ET 2020 work and other European strategies;
- Build upon UNESCO, Eurostat and OECD (UOE) data collection systems, as well as those used by the Agency and other international sources;
- Be applicable to the open method of co-ordination, as used by the European Commission, in order for data to be used for comparative purposes to measure agreed benchmarks.

Experts indicated that future work on mapping inclusive education should foster synergies between stakeholders involved in data collection, in the form of closer alignment in data collection activities and work. A synergy of efforts would involve identifying data needed at the European level compared to that needed at national level in order to define common benchmarks for short, mid and long term work (as outlined above).

It would also support clarification of what type of information is useful for public debate at the European level – who is the target audience and why do they need this information?

A synergy of efforts would also help to clarify the potential consequences of differences between definitions of key terms in different international documents – i.e. the UNESCO 2011 definition of special needs education and how this compares with and/or subsumes the UNCRPD 2006 definition of disability.

Experts involved in the project called for closer co-operation between key international organisations (DG-EAC, Eurostat, Agency, OECD, etc.) on inclusive education issues. Such co-operation would facilitate the improved use of data that is already being collected – for example within the OECD PISA survey (OECD 2000, 2003, 2006, 2007, 2010).

Such co-operation would crucially act as a driver for including issues relating to inclusive education in existing data collection procedures as well as further developing necessary systems of quantitative and qualitative information collection.

However, all experts agreed that European level data should only be collected in line with agreed definitions of key terms and parameters. Such definitions could potentially be based on a synopsis of different national definitions to identify differences and commonalities. Alternatively already existing definitions within data collection systems – ISCED, Eurostat, OECD, ICF classification, Labour Force Survey (LFS) – could be used.

7.4 Framing the agenda within a platform for co-operation

The MIPIE project experts suggested that the synergies needed for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education require work to be framed within a recognised platform enabling stakeholders involved in European data collection work to collaborate effectively, to share knowledge and expertise and to define common perspectives. Such a platform would be to co-ordinate the different sources of international, European and national level work and present this to all stakeholders as a coherent whole.

Such a platform would aim to support the work of other key stakeholders in this arena. This would potentially include:

- Supporting Eurostat where appropriate, in implementing its current data collection enquiry, in identifying the conditions for the development of more extensive quantitative indicators on inclusive education at the European level and in developing sets of qualitative indicators that policy makers may require to monitor their inclusive education policies over time;
- Providing information relevant to the European Commission ET 2020 strategic objectives relating to equity and social cohesion, as well as the European 2010–2020 disability strategy;
- Supporting Eurydice in identifying common areas of information on inclusive education within countries, to be provided within the Key Data and Eurybase frameworks;
- Supporting other international organisations, such as UNESCO and the OECD to include issues relating to inclusive education in their wider education data collection systems and their more general inter-regional dialogues.

Such a platform would have a clear role in supporting countries in implementing the requirements of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. A request repeatedly made during the MIPIE project was for examples of innovative practice in national level data collection to be shared, providing the opportunity to learn from data collection approaches in other countries.

A European platform could support country data collection work relating to inclusive education by:

- Exploring current data collection work, identifying country differences and commonalities so as to provide opportunities for countries to learn from each other, as well as move towards shared approaches for data collection;
- Working with already agreed international definitions – such as the UNCRPD definition of disability, the UNESCO definition of special needs education or the OECD disabilities, learning difficulties, disadvantages typology – alongside national level definitions and parameters for data collection;
- Elaborating upon the proposals outlined above in order to define a long-term agreed agenda for data collection systems that support the implementation of ET 2020 objectives as well as national priorities for inclusive education.

Given work currently being conducted and also planned for the mid and long term, it is argued that the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education is in a position to fulfil the role of providing a platform for further co-operation in this field. The Agency is able to work directly with policy makers and data collection experts from member countries, as well as potentially involve representatives of key research networks and other stakeholder groups in work on the relevant issues. Most importantly, the Agency is able to support the work of other international organisations via its established collaborative links at European and international levels.

Chapter 7 summary

Through a consideration of all of the proposals from the MIPIE project, a proposed agenda for future developments in data collection at the European level can be identified, built upon a synergy of efforts at European and national levels.

European level data collection work requires short, mid and long-term strategies. In the short term, the data collection strategy should be based upon the current Eurostat enquiry into quantitative data collection for special needs education and should carefully explore useful data within existing datasets.

In the mid-term, a European data collection strategy would focus upon the implementation of article 24 of the UNCRRPD and investigate precisely which key information and data may be required, examine whether such data exists and clarify what work is required to gather the data that may be additionally needed.

In the long-term, a data collection strategy should follow a clearly agreed agenda with countries working within a shared framework. MIPIE project experts argued for a comprehensive set of data collection agreements covering concepts, definitions and methods that could be implemented at the national level as a 'minimum' for countries' data collection work.

This agenda would be based on the premise that inclusive education is a quality imperative and it would work to provide countries with quantitative and qualitative insights into the effectiveness of inclusive education policy and the quality of inclusive education practice in terms of monitoring learners' rights and ensuring equity.

For this European agenda to be enacted, four areas of agreement need to be reached across countries in order to support European level work:

- Identify evidence required at national and at international levels;
- Identify the most effective data available as well as data that still needs to be developed;
- Define coherent data gathering procedures and mechanisms at European and at national level;
- Address comparability issues.

If country data is to effectively reflect practice, synergies between key stakeholders at national level need to be based upon a clear rationale for data collection considering national, regional, school and classroom level data.

Any data collected for European level must clearly build upon existing national level data collection, directly link to the ET2020 work and other European strategies and build upon UNESCO, Eurostat and OECD (UOE) data collection systems, as well as those used by the Agency and other international sources.

Future European level work should foster synergies between stakeholders, in the form of closer alignment in data collection activities and work. The synergies needed for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education require work to be framed within a coherent platform enabling stakeholders involved in European data collection work to collaborate effectively, to share knowledge and expertise and to define common perspectives.

Such a platform – potentially based upon the work of the Agency – would aim to support the work of other European stakeholders in this arena as well as support country data collection work relating to inclusive education.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

The overall goal of the MIPIE project has been to build on existing work being undertaken at national and European levels. Using information collected from countries during the project, recommendations in the form of an outline agenda for future national and European level data collection has been developed, to be used for mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education.

By drawing upon work previously conducted at the European level by the Agency, Eurostat, OECD and other organisations and by considering this in line with information on country data collection work collected specifically for this project, this report has attempted to:

- Develop a rationale for what information needs to be made available for policy makers;
- Identify what information is already available and highlight gaps in current information;
- Propose a framework for future mapping work;
- Outline how current work at the national level can potentially be developed in order to collect specific data in line with the proposed framework;
- Describe an agenda for future European level data collection work.

In considering all of the findings and proposals presented in this document, it is possible to highlight a number of key messages that must guide future work in the area of mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education:

(i) The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006) as well as the European Disability Strategy 2010–2020 and the ET 2020 strategic objective relating to equity in education all act as key drivers for inclusive education in countries. All of these international policy initiatives require systematic data collection to provide evidence of country compliance with relevant articles and objectives for inclusive education.

(ii) There is a widespread awareness that evidenced-based policy making is critical for the long-term development of systems of inclusive education. Policy makers, data collection experts and researchers are aware of the need for data collection at national level that meets the requirements of international policy guidelines, and also works within a shared approach to promote a synergy of efforts at national and international levels. However, whilst the need for such data is clear, the methods and procedures for collecting and analysing that data in the best ways is far less clear.

(iii) There is a need for all organisations working at the European level to engage in collaboration and a permanent exchange of information so as to maximise efforts and support national level work in the best possible way.

(iv) There is a need for wide ranging information to be available to policy makers and a variety of complementary approaches to data collection to be taken by different organisations at both national and European levels.

All countries agree that mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education is a complex and multi-faceted task. This report aims to present an initial step in mapping the current work being undertaken at national and European levels. However it is considered that the concrete proposals outlined in this report have the potential to be used as the basis for more detailed and long-term research involving the collection of qualitative and quantitative data that can be used for monitoring purposes and to support current European level initiatives in this area – notably the Eurostat enquiry focussing upon special needs education – as well as country level work.

ANNEX: INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN LEVEL DATA COLLECTION WORK

The sections below describe the work currently being conducted by key international and European organisations involved in educational data collection that can be related to mapping policy for inclusive education. Essentially, these sections present a descriptive, situation analysis of current data collection activities at international and European levels.

These are not the only organisations involved in data collection or dissemination – the work of, for example, the Council of Europe or UNICEF could also have been included. However, a decision was taken to specifically consider the work of these organisations as they have either been directly involved in, or their work has been repeatedly referred to within the context of the MIPIE project discussions.

These descriptions attempt *as far as possible* to address the following issues in relation to each organisation:

- What type of data is collected in relation to inclusive education and how is this done?
- What information is disseminated in relation to inclusive education and why?

United Nations Education Scientific and Culture Organisation (UNESCO)

The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) is the official statistical office for UNESCO. It collects and disseminates global statistics on education, mainly focussing upon policy issues and topics. UIS works on the World Education Indicators (WEI) programme which collects detailed statistics in the form of cross-national studies.

The data collection work of UNESCO in relation to inclusive education has two important and inter-connected strands – firstly monitoring movements towards Education for All (EFA) at the global level and secondly providing international guidelines relating to key concepts used as the basis for data gathering.

The EFA initiative is a response to global concerns regarding the numbers of children who do not attend school, or who underachieve generally. The first United Nations World Conference on Education for All (EFA) was held in Jomtien in Thailand in 1990 and since then a number of international declarations and conventions have focussed upon EFA. Most notably, UNESCO's Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education was adopted in 1994 (UNESCO, 1994), followed by the Dakar Framework for Action (UNESCO, 2000) and the International Conference on Education in Geneva (UNESCO, IBE, 2009).

EFA highlights the learning needs of marginalised groups and looks at achievement, not just school attendance. This is a challenge for all countries including those in Europe where many children are excluded or do not meaningfully participate in schooling or other educational programmes. EFA and an inclusive approach to education are inextricably linked and UNESCO calls upon member states to: *'adopt an inclusive education approach in the design, implementation, monitoring and assessment of educational policies as a way to further accelerate the attainment of Education for All (EFA) goals as well as to contribute to building more inclusive societies.'* (UNESCO, IBE, 2009, p. 18). UNESCO encourages member states to: *'collect and use relevant data on all categories of the excluded to better develop education policies and reforms for their inclusion, as well as to develop national monitoring and evaluation mechanisms'* (UNESCO, IBE, 2009, p. 19).

The UNESCO Policy Guidelines (2009) document suggests that: *'Inclusive education is a process of strengthening the capacity of the education system to reach out to all learners ... An 'inclusive' education system can only be created if ordinary schools become more*

inclusive – in other words, if they become better at educating all children in their communities.' (UNESCO, 2009, p. 8).

The work of UNESCO clearly indicates how inclusive education is a question of equity and is therefore a quality issue impacting upon all learners. Three propositions regarding inclusive education are highlighted:

- Inclusion and quality are reciprocal;
- Access and quality are linked and are mutually reinforcing;
- Quality and equity are central to ensuring inclusive education.

The Policy Guidelines argue that a: *'needs analysis must proceed the formulation of policies and plans'*, that *'systems and methods of collecting education-related data are necessary to inform policy and practice'* and that *'monitoring and evaluation are necessary to improve planning and implementation'* (2009, p. 24).

The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) established an EFA observatory to monitor and report on progress towards EFA and this led to the production of the first EFA monitoring report in 2001 aimed at describing progress towards the EFA goals and *'holding governments and the international community accountable for the promises made in Dakar'*. (UNESCO, 2011) Since then, UNESCO has published an annual EFA Global Monitoring Report (GMR) which uses data from many sources.

The UNESCO 2011 report on Enhancing Effectiveness of EFA Co-ordination suggests that: *'For progress towards EFA to be sustained and accelerated will require strong political will and national leadership to ensure that governments prioritize ... Further progress will require existing gaps in data, policy, capacity, governance and financing to narrow.'* (p. 2).

The authors suggest that the mobilisation of the necessary resources for EFA in all countries includes financial resources for EFA programmes, but also technical resources for capacity development, policy-making and implementation, and importantly data management and monitoring and evaluation of policy implementation.

UNESCO has made a major contribution to specific data collection for learners with special educational needs as a result of the *Recommendation concerning the International Standardization of Educational Statistics* in 1958. In 1978, UNESCO Member States developed a classification tool known as the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), which was revised in 1997. The ISCED document was designed to serve as an: *'instrument suitable for assembling, compiling, and presenting statistics of education both within individual countries and internationally'* (UNESCO, 1997, p. 1).

The ISCED (UNESCO, 1997) discussion of special educational needs expands on this by highlighting the fact that 'special educational needs' is a broader term than disability; it covers more 'types' of educational need – for example social, emotional and behavioural difficulties – and is clearly a context bound definition: *'... the concept of 'children with special educational needs' extends beyond those who may be included in handicapped categories to cover those who are failing in school for a wide variety of other reasons that are known to be likely to impede a child's optimal progress. Whether or not this more broadly defined group of children are in need of additional support depends on the extent to which schools need to adapt their curriculum, teaching and organisation and/or to provide additional human or material resources so as to stimulate efficient and effective learning for these pupils.'* (p. 42).

In 2011, UNESCO published a revised definition focussing upon special needs education – as opposed to special educational needs. This is a definition based on the notion of

additional resources, with special needs education being defined as: *‘Education designed to facilitate the learning of individuals who, for a wide variety of reasons, require additional support and adaptive pedagogical methods in order to participate and meet learning objectives in an educational programme. Reasons may include (but are not limited to) disadvantages in physical, behavioural, intellectual, emotional and social capacities. Educational programmes in special needs education may follow a similar curriculum as that offered in the parallel regular education system, however they take individuals’ particular needs into account by providing specific resources (e.g. specially trained personnel, equipment, or space) and, if appropriate, modified educational content or learning objectives. These programmes can be offered for individual learners within already existing educational programmes, or be offered as a separate class in the same or separate educational institutions’.* (p. 83)

Learners with special educational needs are defined by the additional resources provided to support their education in a systematic and long term way. This definition has the potential to be used in many data collection arenas and by other organisations – please see the relevant section below for information on how Eurostat is considering the use of this definition in relation to European level data collection.

World Health Organisation (WHO)

The World Health Organisation has developed a series of classification tools mainly to address the issues of developing internationally comparable tools to conceptualise, classify and understand disease (ICD-10), functioning and disability (ICF), health interventions (ICHI) and comparing data about disability worldwide. The WHO family of Classifications (WHO-FIC) includes different classification tools and products (e.g. ICD₁ and its revisions, ICIDH₂, ICF₃, ICF – CY₄) that can be used to compare health data and health information worldwide. Among the different classification systems, the ICF, is an attempt to move away from the limitations embedded in the clinical/medical model of disability to a model which takes into account environmental barriers. One of the most recent tools of classification used to identify and define disability is the International Classification of Functioning Disability and Health (WHO, 2001). This is internationally known as the ‘bio-psycho-social’ model of disability (WHO, 2001, p. 20). Unlike the previous classification tools (see ICD-10, 1990) the ICF is capable of identifying circumstantial and environmental factors rather than focusing only on individuals and their functional disorders.

The ICF is concerned with the analysis of all conditions – biological and environmental – that may represent a limitation or a hindrance for. It provides a framework based on scientific evidence to screen all disabling barriers, both social and individual, that may restrict the activity and limit the participation of individuals in their everyday lives. Such barriers may include impairments, discriminatory policies, the lack of accessibility to places, the shortage of service delivery and the poor design of products.

In the ICF, disability is defined as the new ‘umbrella term’ (WHO, 2001) to indicate impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions. The ICF (WHO, 2001) consists of two main parts:

- 1) Functioning and Disability;
- 2) Contextual Factors.

These two parts are then sub-divided into four components:

- 1a) Body Functions and Structures;

1b) Activities and Participation;

2a) Environmental Factors;

2b) Personal Factors.

These four sections are equally important for the identification and classification of disability, as they take into account biological elements (such as body functions and structures) and what the person can do (such as activities and participation), as well as elements external to the individual (such as environmental and personal factors).

The ICD-10 is currently undergoing a major revision. The ICD-11 is expected in 2015 and will aim to align ICF and ICD, for example by identifying the functional properties of diseases and re-defining diseases that are impairments of body functions such as 'mental retardation'.

WHO does not specifically focus upon issues for inclusive education; however, within the much larger remit of its international level work, consideration is given to the situation of children with disabilities globally.

Generally, disability issues are addressed by the Disability and Rehabilitation (DAR) team who work towards the enhancement of the quality of life of persons with disabilities and the promotion of the rights and dignity of persons with disabilities (WHO, 2011). One aspect of this work is the facilitation of data collection, analysis and dissemination of disability-related data and information.

In 2011, the World Report on Disability was produced in collaboration with the World Bank. (See: http://www.who.int/disabilities/world_report/2011/report/en/index.html). Chapter 2 of this report debates evidence and data collection in relation to international disability issues. In this chapter it is argued that: *'Disability, a complex multidimensional experience, poses several challenges for measurement. Approaches to measuring disability vary across countries and influence the results. Operational measures of disability vary according to the purpose and application of the data, the conception of disability, the aspects of disability examined – impairments, activity limitations, participation restrictions, related health conditions, environmental factors – the definitions, question design, reporting sources, data collection methods, and expectations of functioning.'* (p. 21).

However, the need for reliable data is stressed: *'Robust evidence helps to make well informed decisions about disability policies and programmes'*. (p. 21).

Chapter 7 of the report focuses upon education and children with disabilities. Several sources of information – WHO studies, UNESCO reports, EFA monitoring reports, OECD work, Agency work (SNE country data and thematic studies), as well as specific country research studies – are used. A specific recommendation in the conclusions of the chapter on education is the need to establish monitoring and evaluation systems in relation to the development of country policies: *'Data on the numbers of learners with disabilities and their educational needs, both in special schools and in mainstream schools, can often be collected through existing service providers. Research is needed on the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of inclusive education'*. (p. 226)

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

In the 1990s, OECD undertook a 'Special Study on Statistics and Indicators' to improve the comparability of data with relation to learners with different needs across countries. The main aim was to align the different classification systems in use in each member country and reduce their impact upon the process of collecting and comparing statistical data concerning the number of learners identified as having special educational needs.

OECD work at that time indicated that differences in the number of disabled learners and related statements of 'special educational needs', often resulted from different interpretations of the definition of 'special educational needs' and most importantly, from different administrative, bureaucratic and political measures which influence assessment procedures.

With this in mind, the OECD (2004, 2007) developed a tri-partite classification and categorisation system where learners identified in countries as having SEN were placed into one of three cross-national macro categories relating the particular types of educational resources and provision.

This model is known as the DDD model (Disability, Difficulty and Disadvantage) and is based on the idea that data should be collected in relation to the additional human, financial and material resources and provision allocated to learners, which are potentially more easily identifiable and comparable across countries. (More details are available from www.oecd.org/edu/equity/senddd). The OECD work takes the ISCED 1997 as a starting point, with special educational needs identified by the additional resources provided to support a learner's education. This involves transforming the national legal frameworks and category systems into a tripartite categorisation system based on the national categories that individual countries use within their data base, subdivided into three broad cross-national categories based on perceived causes of educational failure.

Within the work, both qualitative and quantitative information is collected via electronic questionnaires that ask for data according to the A, B, C categories as defined in the DDD taxonomy, relating to learners in mainstream and separate special education schools and classes.

In 2009, the SENDDD approach was adopted within a joint study of work in the Baltic States, Eastern European countries and Malta by the OECD and the Centre for Research on Lifelong Learning (CRELL) within the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (OECD and European Commission, 2009, for more details please see <http://crell.jrc.ec.europa.eu/SENDDD>).

The resulting information from the SENDDD project work has been used in a number of different OECD publications including *Education for all* (2003), *Society at a Glance* (2002, 2005) and the specific publication *Students with disabilities, learning difficulties and disadvantages: Policies, statistics and indicators* (OECD, 2007). SENDDD indicator information has also been used in the European Commission, DG-EAC's progress reports relating to the Lisbon Objectives.

Although this work is no longer being undertaken by the OECD, many countries currently gather information on learners with SEN within the PISA survey (OECD, 2007). In 2003, this data was collected through an optional test instrument designed to be used in schools where all learners have special educational needs, or are primary school learners, and where the regular test booklet would be considered inappropriate. The special educational needs booklet (UH booklet) includes the PISA items deemed to be most suitable for learners with SEN and the test is designed to be only one hour in length, instead of the standard two hour assessment. Data provides information on the learner: performance; demographic characteristics; educational experience and expectations; and perception of school, as well as information on characteristics of effective learning behaviours.

The TALIS survey includes special needs issues in the questionnaire designed for teachers working in mainstream schools, but also includes teachers working exclusively with learners with SEN. It provides information on the importance given in schools'

appraisal and feedback policy for teaching learners with SEN and on teaching in multicultural settings.

Within the project *Pathways for students with disabilities to tertiary education and to employment*, the OECD conducted country reviews on the implementation of inclusive education policies in six OECD countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Ireland, Norway, United States). Information is provided on countries' policies according to the following factors: definitions of disability; existing data; policy; funding schemes; educational provision for learners with SEN; existing support services; teacher training and parental and community involvement.

This project also included a longitudinal study in some other OECD countries (France, Denmark, Norway, Czech Republic and the Netherlands) that aimed to describe the quality of transition processes beyond upper secondary and tertiary education (OECD, 2011). Information is provided on learners who finished upper secondary education (with or without a qualification) in 2007 and on learners who finished their undergraduate level (with or without a qualification) in the same year. The questionnaire was framed around various descriptors:

- A descriptor on participation describing the activity of learners 2 years after leaving upper secondary or tertiary education;
- A performance descriptor dealing with the quality of the educational environment experienced by learners during the 2006/07 school/academic year;
- A transition descriptor dealing with the continuity and consistency of learners' pathways during the transition period;
- An affiliation descriptor linking the quality of transition programmes to the abilities acquired by learners and their sense of belonging.

European Commission

The work of the European Union is guided by the EU 2020 strategy (please see http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/index_en.htm for more information.) Within the EU 2020 work, the needs of people with disabilities are generally considered within five 'flagship initiatives':

- European platform against Poverty;
- Agenda for new Skills and Jobs;
- Youth on the Move;
- Innovative Union;
- Digital Agenda for Europe.

However, in November 2010, the *European Disability Strategy 2010/2020: a renewed commitment to a barrier-free Europe* was adopted in order to ensure that the specific needs of people with disabilities are considered in all EU level work. The main objectives of the strategy are to:

- Empower people with disabilities to enjoy their full rights;
- Create a barrier-free Europe for all;
- Comply with the international commitments including the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

The European Commission has different administrative units called Directorate Generals (DGs), responsible for community programmes and initiatives in designated areas relating to civil society. Two DGs are involved in work that directly impacts upon people with disabilities, as well as data collection and dissemination impacting upon education: DG Education and Culture and DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion.

The objectives of Europe 2020 and the European Disability Strategy guide the work of both the DG Education and Culture and DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion; the work of both the units in relation to relevant aspects of data collection for mapping purposes are considered in the sections below.

DG Education and Culture

The European Commission Staff Working Document relating to the European Disability Strategy lists a number of key actions relating to the thematic area: *‘increase knowledge on education levels and opportunities of people with disabilities including “Collect data on access and participation of persons with high dependency needs, including persons with very severe intellectual disabilities, in the education system”’*.

Following the principle of subsidiarity, DG-EAC does not directly engage in data collection for education, but rather uses country sources, such as peer learning exercises, information collected in relation to European reference tools (e.g. European Qualification Framework, key competences framework, etc.) and information from other international organisations (such as Eurostat, the OECD, CRELL and the Agency).

This approach is reflected in the annual EU progress report for education, which is structured in chapters in line with the strategic objectives of the ET 2020 Strategy:

1. Making lifelong learning and mobility a reality;
2. Improving the quality and efficiency of education and training;
3. Promoting equity, social cohesion and active citizenship;
4. Enhancing creativity and innovation, including entrepreneurship, at all levels of education and training.

Strategic objective 3 – Promoting equity, social cohesion and active citizenship - explicitly addresses special educational needs: *‘Educational disadvantage should be addressed by providing high quality early childhood education and targeted support, and by promoting inclusive education. Education and training systems should aim to ensure that all learners – including those from disadvantaged backgrounds, those with special needs and migrants – complete their education, including, where appropriate, through second-chance education and the provision of more personalised learning.’* (Council conclusions on ET 2020, May 2009, p. 7)

The monitoring and analysis of progress is undertaken via five benchmarks for education. 16 indicators are used for data collection with SEN being one such indicator. Data collection in relation to this indicator has now been charged to Eurostat. This work is considered in detail in the relevant section below.

Work from various DG-EAC sources suggests that quantitative data combined with qualitative information considering different aspects of inclusive and special needs education are important for developing European level understanding of the issues surrounding equity in education.

DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

The EU Disability Strategy 2020 very much impacts upon the work of DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG-EMPL). Whilst education is not the direct focus of DG-EMPL's work, a number of activities touch upon educational issues and specifically upon the need for data in relation to the education of people with disabilities.

In 2007, DG-EMPL published a report on people with disabilities – *Study of compilation of disability statistical data from the administrative registers of the Member States* (See: <http://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=3007&langId=en>). The report uses data from a range of sources and presents statistics on various aspects of the experiences of people with disabilities including invalidity pensions, participation in the labour market and access to services and independent living. One chapter focuses upon education and considers which categories are covered by the SNE legislation in countries. This draws mainly on data from the Agency and Eurydice, as well as statistical data on placements and resources for learners identified as having SEN from a range of sources (again the Agency and Eurydice, as well as the OECD and national education statistics).

DG-EMPL also supports the work of dedicated networks examining the situation of people with disabilities. One such network is the Academic Network of European Disability Experts (ANED). The 2009 ANED report: *Indicators of Disability Equality in Europe (IDEE)* proposes a preliminary list of indicators for further discussion, including, in chapter 7, the areas for the development of quantitative and qualitative indicators for inclusive education. These proposals were built upon in the 2010 ANED report *Inclusive education for young disabled people in Europe: trends, issues and challenges* which highlights recommendations aimed at supporting inclusion policies, including:

- Foster education policies that combine effectiveness and equity at all levels of education to prevent drop out and foster success;
- Build reliable indicators and statistical data to support effective planning and monitoring of education and training policies.

The report suggests that the European Commission could further support countries in this area by promoting programmes to share good practice and expertise in tools and devices (including data collection), but most importantly supporting the definition of quality indicators for inclusion at all levels of education.

Eurostat

Eurostat is the European Union organisation for the collection, processing and dissemination of statistical data (see: <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/quality/introduction>).

Eurostat collaborates with UNESCO and the OECD to collect and report on statistics and indicators in education – the UOE (UNESCO, OECD, Eurostat) data collection on education systems. This work covers many aspects of education within the lifelong learning context, but at present data collection is not specifically related to inclusive or special needs education issues. Within the UOE work there is currently no agreed definition of special education adopted by countries that can be used as a basis for collecting consistent and comparable statistics.

Within the Council Conclusions on a coherent framework of indicators and benchmarks from May 2007 (OJ/C311/10 and document 2007-ETS-02.3EN), an indicator on SEN was proposed and adopted. The Council Conclusions suggested that the indicator would: ‘... largely be based on existing data [but] whose definition still needs further clarification’. In these conclusions the Council invites the Commission: ‘to submit to the Council, for further

consideration, information on the definition of the following indicators – special needs education’ and as a result Eurostat was charged with developing this work.

In the Eurostat work programme for 2011, three key tasks are outlined:

1. An enquiry to ‘actors’ at international and country level regarding data and indicator needs in relation to learners with SEN. The enquiry will also include questions on data availability at country level as well as possibilities for making data ‘comparable’;
2. Creation of an ‘ideal’ UOE test table combining policy needs and data availability in an ‘optimal mix’, to be accompanied by relevant methodological instructions including concepts and definitions to be followed;
3. Identification of relevant possible indicators given policy requirements and available data.

In relation to this third task, a number of key parameters have been identified by Eurostat. Any system of indicators should be:

- Policy-relevant, by being capable of providing clear and unambiguous responses to key policy issues and concerns;
- User friendly, i.e., comprehensible, timely and few in number;
- Derived from a framework, which allows the interpretation of one figure (say enrolment) in the context of other basic variables (e.g. demography and investment in education) of a particular country;
- Technically sound, i.e. valid, reliable and comparable;
- Feasible to measure at reasonable cost, in that the basic statistics required are either readily available or comparatively easy to collect within a well-defined timeframe.

Several challenges regarding data collection on SEN that need to be addressed have been acknowledged by Eurostat. Notably any future data collection in this area needs to comply with the UOE framework, whilst meeting EU 2020 strategy needs.

Currently within the work, it is proposed that core indicators could potentially focus upon:

- Numbers of segregated/included learners with SEN, in absolute terms or as a percentage of all learners with SEN;
- The distribution of learners with SEN by setting.

Indicators can also be added to in order to expand upon SEN specific issues to cover all equity aspects:

- Access (early identification of learners with SEN, additional provision);
- Treatment (additional resources and staffing);
- Outcomes (graduation and employability).

Eurostat suggests that given the complexity and inherent difficulties of the subject matter, in order for quantitative information in the form of an indicator to be put into a clear context, wide ranging qualitative information from different national and international sources will be needed for policy making and monitoring.

Eurydice

Eurydice is a permanent network of education information providers within the Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency of the European Commission. The network is comprised of the 27 EU member states, plus Iceland, Lichtenstein, Norway and Turkey.

The work and information disseminated via the Eurydice network mainly focuses on how education systems in Europe are structured and organised at all levels. Eurydice produces a huge resource of information providing country descriptions and overviews of national education systems, well as indicators and statistics (produced in the Key Data series of publications). Some editions in the Key Data on Education series have included statistical data on learners with SEN, provided by the Agency among other sources.

Within the country descriptions of education systems, Chapter 10 provides overviews of systems for special needs education in countries – mainly descriptive, qualitative information. (See: http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/education/eurydice/eurybase_en.php).

In 2012, the current information will be revised and replaced by a new 'European Encyclopaedia on National Education Systems' providing descriptions of education systems from all 33 countries participating in the EU Lifelong Learning Programme (EU Member States, Croatia, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey). The revised information will cover qualitative data on SEN provision.

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (the Agency)

The European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education has a mandate from the Ministers of Education in the member countries to facilitate collaboration regarding country priorities that are in line with the Council priorities as identified in the ET 2020 strategy and in accordance with international agreements such as the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006). The Agency works to this mandate via the collection, analysis and transfer of accurate and reliable national and European level information that can be related to individual countries' national contexts.

The Agency's main focus is upon the collection of qualitative data and information relating to priority topics identified by member country representatives. All of this information is made available in reports and web based information in up to 21 languages, available from: www.european-agency.org

However, the availability of comparative statistical data relating to special and inclusive education is also an acknowledged priority for member countries. In 2010, a survey of Agency member countries explored the potential indicators that they considered as being a priority for them.

Currently the Agency collects data from official Ministerial sources. All data refers to learners officially identified as having SEN as defined in the country in question. The data uses the country based, legal definitions of SEN as there are no accepted definitions of SEN available to use comparatively. Data provided by countries covers eight agreed questions – five are statistical:

1. Number of compulsory school aged learners (including those with SEN).
2. Number of compulsory school aged learners who have SEN (in all educational settings).
3. Learners with SEN in segregated special schools.
4. Learners with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools.
5. Learners with SEN in inclusive settings.

The information submitted is raw data, i.e. actual numbers of learners registered in different settings.

The three remaining questions provide contextual information with notes and clarifications, particularly referring to legal definitions of special needs:

6. Compulsory age range with a specification of primary and secondary age phases if appropriate.

7. Clarification of public and private sector education.

8. The legal definition of SEN in the country.

The complete data set – the last being from 2010 – is available from:
<http://www.european-agency.org/publications/ereports/special-needs-education-country-data-2010/special-needs-education-country-data-2010>

GLOSSARY

Preamble

Within the early project discussions it was agreed to collate a Glossary of Key Terms used in the project in order to have a shared language for all participants to use in relation to data collection work. Different sources for definitions have been used for this Glossary:

- Existing definitions that are already in use at the international level;
- Key literature quotations and citations;
- Operational definitions developed within the MIPIE project.

The Key terms listed below are not presented in alphabetical order, but rather are grouped around key themes for the MIPIE project.

Key Terms

Indicator – Quantitative or qualitative factor or variable that provides a simple and reliable means to measure achievement, to reflect the changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance of a development factor.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms: <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/>)

Quantitative data – Quantitative data is data expressing a certain quantity, amount or range. Usually, there are measurement units associated with the data, e.g. metres, in the case of the height of a person. It makes sense to set boundary limits to such data, and it is also meaningful to apply arithmetic operations to the data.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms)

Qualitative data – Qualitative data is data describing the attributes or properties that an object possesses. The properties are categorized into classes that may be assigned numeric values. However, there is no significance to the data values themselves, they simply represent attributes of the object concerned.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms)

Quantitative indicator – A factor or variable that provides a simple and reliable means to measure a certain quantity, amount or range of achievement, to reflect the changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance of a development factor.

(A project operational definition, developed using the indicator and quantitative data definitions above)

Qualitative indicator – A factor or variable that provides a simple and reliable means to describe the attributes or properties that an object possesses, to reflect the changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance of a development factor.

(A project operational definition, developed using the indicator and qualitative data definitions above)

Benchmark – A reference point or standard against which performance or achievements can be assessed. A benchmark refers to the performance that has been achieved in the recent past by other comparable organisations, or what can be reasonably inferred to have been achieved in the circumstances.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms)

Quality assurance – Quality assurance encompasses any activity that is concerned with assessing and improving the merit or the worth of a development intervention or its compliance with given standards. Note: examples of quality assurance activities include appraisal, reviews during implementation, evaluations, etc. Quality assurance may also refer to the assessment of the quality of a portfolio and its development effectiveness.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms)

Monitoring – A continuing function that uses systematic collection of data on specified indicators to provide management and the main stakeholders of an ongoing development intervention with indications of the extent of progress and achievement of objectives and progress in the use of allocated funds. Related terms: performance monitoring, indicator.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms)

Mapping – The collation of a wide range of indicator and data sources in order to provide an overall picture of policy situations and developments.

(A project operational definition)

System input – The financial, human, and material resources used in education, e.g. the characteristics of learners, educators, curricula, textbooks, facilities and equipment, and financial resources.

(European Research Associates: <http://www.erabrussels.be/home.htm>)

System process – Interactions between learners and inputs, between different inputs themselves, and between teaching/learning processes, e.g. attendance/participation, absenteeism, etc.

(European Research Associates)

System outcomes – The ultimate or eventual effects of education, e.g. increased earnings, employment, contribution to productivity, improved health, and other non-monetary outcomes.

(European Research Associates)

Outputs – The direct and more immediate results or effects of education, e.g. learner's completion/certification.

(European Research Associates)

Effectiveness – Effectiveness means the extent to which the activity's stated objectives have been met.

(OECD, Glossary of Statistical Terms)

Equity – Defining equity, the Commission of the European Communities (2006) states that it is: '*... viewed as the extent to which individuals can take advantage of education and training, in terms of opportunities, access, treatment and outcomes*' (p. 2).

(Commission of the European Communities (2006) *Communication from the Commission to the Council and to the European Parliament. Efficiency and equity in European education and training systems*. Brussels, 8.9.2006 COM(2006) 481 final http://ec.europa.eu/education/policies/2010/doc/comm481_en.pdf)

The OECD (2007) links equity to fairness and states that personal and social circumstances should not be an obstacle to achieving educational potential.

(OECD (2007) *No more failures: Ten steps to equity in education*, OECD, Paris)

Inclusion – Concerns issues of gender, ethnicity, class, social conditions, health and human rights encompassing universal involvement, access, participation and achievement (Ouane, A. 2008. *Creating education systems which offer opportunities for lifelong learning*. Paper presented at UNESCO International Conference on Education ‘Inclusive education: the way of the future’ 48th session. Geneva, 25–28 November, 2008)

Inclusive education – The UNESCO (2008) definition states that inclusive education is: *‘an ongoing process aimed at offering quality education for all while respecting diversity and the different needs and abilities, characteristics and learning expectations of the students and communities, eliminating all forms of discrimination’* (p. 3). UNESCO-IBE, 2008. *Conclusions and recommendations of the 48th session of the International Conference on Education*. Geneva, Switzerland. UNESCO IBE.ED/BIE/CONFINTED 48/5

Special needs education – the new 2011 ISCED definition currently being discussed, defines special needs education as an:

‘Education designed to facilitate the learning of individuals who, for a wide variety of reasons, require additional support and adaptive pedagogical methods in order to participate and meet learning objectives in an educational programme. Reasons may include (but are not limited to) disadvantages in physical, behavioural, intellectual, emotional and social capacities. Educational programmes in special needs education may follow a similar curriculum as that offered in the parallel regular education system, however they take individuals’ particular needs into account by providing specific resources (e.g. specially trained personnel, equipment, or space) and, if appropriate, modified educational content or learning objectives. These programmes can be offered for individual learners within already existing educational programmes, or be offered as a separate class in the same or separate educational institutions’. (p. 83)

School for all – School for all means inclusive education for all individuals in mainstream ... regardless of the level of education and training. Education in a mainstream environment is the fundamental principle of the School for all. Inclusive education must guarantee quality and should offer lifelong equality of access for everyone.

(Charter of Luxembourg, 1996)

Descriptor – A category name used to identify a grouping of quantitative and/or qualitative indicators.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on participation in education – Refers to equity in access and relates the quality of inclusive education policies to their ability to foster equality in terms of access and ensure that learners with SEN are not excluded from any level of the general education system on the basis of their disability or special needs.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on access to appropriate support – Refers to equity in relation to educational opportunities. It relates quality to access to additional resources and the extent to which these resources facilitate effective education from both a quantitative and a qualitative point of view.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on learning success and transition opportunities – Refers to equity in terms of achievement opportunities and relates quality to the ability of education systems to enable learners with SEN to have *the same achievement opportunities* as their peers.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on Affiliation opportunities – Refers to equity in relation to personal autonomy. It relates quality to the degree of empowerment learners acquire through their education to make decisions affecting their lives, to assume responsibilities, to actively participate in society and to feel as worthy and valued as their non disabled peers.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on resource allocation – Refers to effectiveness and cost-effectiveness issues and relates quality to the ability of the financial, technical and human resources invested by countries for the education of learners with SEN in both mainstream and special schools and classrooms to meet their objectives at minimum cost.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on admission – Refers to schools' receptiveness to diversity and relates quality to education systems' ability to ease transition opportunities, reduce barriers to attendance and empower learners to be involved in their school community.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on assessment – Refers to quality of learning and relates quality to the ability of the assessment and evaluation procedures to support high quality of learning.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on planning – Refers to quality of support and relates quality to a school's ability to build upon the identification of learners' needs to define all necessary aspects of the teaching and learning process and to implement procedures and tools (e.g. IEPs) required for high quality of support.

(A project operational definition)

Descriptor on teaching – Refers to effectiveness of teaching and relates quality to the classroom teaching practices, class management, co-operation among staff, etc.

List of Abbreviations

UNESCO – United Nations Education Scientific and Culture Organisation
<http://www.unesco.org/new/en/unesco/>

WHO – World Health Organisation <http://www.who.int/en/>

OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development www.oecd.org

DG-EAC – Directorate-General Education and Culture

http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/education_culture/index_en.htm

DG-EMPL – Directorate-General Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

<http://ec.europa.eu/social/home.jsp>

ANED – Academic Network of Experts on Disability <http://www.disability-europe.net/>

CRELL – Centre for Research on Lifelong Learning <http://crell.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

UOE – UNESCO, OECD, Eurostat joint data collection on education systems

<http://www.uis.unesco.org/UISQUESTIONNAIRES/Pages/default.aspx>

Overviews of Key Policy Documents

United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2006

<http://www.un.org/disabilities/default.asp?id=150>

'The Convention is intended as a human rights instrument with an explicit, social development dimension. It adopts a broad categorization of persons with disabilities and reaffirms that all persons with all types of disabilities must enjoy all human rights and fundamental freedoms. It clarifies and qualifies how all categories of rights apply to persons with disabilities and identifies areas where adaptations have to be made for persons with disabilities to effectively exercise their rights and areas where their rights have been violated, and where protection of rights must be reinforced.'

The Convention was negotiated during eight sessions of an Ad Hoc Committee of the General Assembly from 2002 to 2006, making it the human rights treaty negotiated on the fastest time.'

ET 2020 Strategic Framework

The Strategic Framework is an element within the wider Europe 2020 http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/index_en.htm

Europe 2020 has five headline targets, one of them relating to education http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/reaching-the-goals/targets/index_en.htm

'In the period up to 2020, the primary goal of European cooperation should be to support the further development of education and training systems in the Member States which are aimed at ensuring:

(a) the personal, social and professional fulfilment of all citizens;

(b) sustainable economic prosperity and employability, whilst promoting democratic values, social cohesion, active citizenship, and intercultural dialogue.'

The ET 2020 Strategic Framework sets out four strategic objectives for education and training in the coming decade:

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2009:119:0002:0010:EN:PDF>

Strategic objective 3 focuses upon: Promoting equity, social cohesion and active citizenship: *'Education and training policy should enable all citizens, irrespective of their personal, social or economic circumstances, to acquire, update and develop over a lifetime both job-specific skills and the key competences needed for their employability and to foster further learning, active citizenship and intercultural dialogue. Educational disadvantage should be addressed by providing high quality early childhood education and targeted support, and by promoting inclusive education. Education and training systems should aim to ensure that all learners – including those from disadvantaged backgrounds, those with special needs and migrants – complete their education, including, where appropriate, through second-chance education and the provision of more personalised learning. Education should promote intercultural competences, democratic values and respect for fundamental rights and the environment, as well as combat all forms of discrimination, equipping all young people to interact positively with their peers from diverse backgrounds.'*

EU Disability Strategy 2010–2020

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2010:0636:FIN:EN:PDF>

The Strategy provides a framework for action at the European level, as well as at national level to promote a barrier free Europe for the estimated 6 million men, women and children with disabilities across Europe.

'The overall aim of this Strategy is to empower people with disabilities so that they can enjoy their full rights, and benefit fully from participating in society and in the European

economy, notably through the Single market. Achieving this and ensuring effective implementation of the UN Convention across the EU calls for consistency. This Strategy identifies actions at EU level to supplement national ones, and it determines the mechanisms needed to implement the UN Convention at EU level, including inside the EU institutions. It also identifies the support needed for funding, research, awareness-raising, statistics and data collection.'

In the Communication of November 2010 on the strategy, the European Commission proposed to use legislative and other instruments, to optimise accessibility for people with disabilities and the elderly. As a result a public consultation has been launched. See: http://ec.europa.eu/justice/newsroom/discrimination/opinion/111207_en.htm

A European Accessibility Act is proposed for 2012: *'The European Accessibility Act will not aim to change or amend existing EU legislation that refers to general compliance with accessibility requirements without defining accessibility, but will complement it by providing details on what accessibility means for the goods and services addressed by the Act. It will also play the role of legal framework on accessibility for existing EU legislation regulating in detail particular goods or services (including their accessibility).'*
http://ec.europa.eu/justice/discrimination/files/2011-12-13_consultation_background_document.pdf

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All countries need to track the implementation of new educational policies and legislation. The justifications and pressures for mapping such developments are very clear at international, European and national levels.

The pressures on policy makers to demonstrate how policies are leading towards greater educational inclusion results in the need for the systematic collection of qualitative and quantitative information that answers key questions and can be used longitudinally within countries to map national developments, as well as internationally across countries to compare relative developments.

This report presents the final results of the Mapping the Implementation of Policy for Inclusive Education (MIPIE) project. The project recommendations presented here provide a detailed agenda for the future short, mid and long-term data collection required at national and European levels in relation to mapping the implementation of policy for inclusive education.